

EXACTABILITY VERSUS PROBABILITY: CALMING THE CHAOTIC COLLATZ

KENNETH ROGER HUTCHINGS

This paper is dedicated to all the Collatz Rabbit Hunters.

ABSTRACT. The Short-cut function of the Collatz Conjecture, which has remained unproven since 1937, has two potential operations or steps. For all positive integers, if integer $n_{(i-1)}$ is *Even* then $n_i = n_{(i-1)}/2$. If integer $n_{(i-1)}$ is *Odd* then $n_i = (3 * n_{(i-1)} + 1)/2$. The conjecture is that, when applied recursively, eventually, all positive starting integers will result in a terminal periodic sequence of (1, 2) of period 2.

Plotting the sequence of Short-cut function steps for different sub-sets of the positive starting integers, where the y -axis is the number of *Even* steps and the x -axis is the number of *Odd* steps, provides significantly improved empirical evidence of the true nature of the Collatz Short-cut function.

Theorems derived are presented and algebraic and/or logical proofs are provided for each theorem, which when evaluated together, provide logical and exactable, versus probable, proof that the Collatz Conjecture is true.

CONTENTS

1. The Collatz Conjecture	2
2. Outline of the Theorems and Proofs Presented	4
3. Empirical Methodology and Results with Tables and Figures	6
4. Supporting Terms, Definitions, Functions and Equations	24
5. Identical and Alternating Equivalence Parity Theorem	42
6. <i>EV</i> greater than $(\log_2(3) - 1)$ Theorem	44
7. No Terminal Loop other than (1,2,1,2, ... infinity) Theorem	48
8. <i>EL</i> greater than/equal to $\text{Log}_2(\text{no}) + \text{p}(\text{Log}_2(3) - 1)$ Theorem	49
9. Reductio Ad Absurdum Collatz Conjecture Theorem	55
10. A Parable, Consequences and Other Interesting Items	58
List of Figures	62
List of Tables	62
References	63

Date: January 24, 2025.

2020 Mathematics Subject Classification. Primary 06A07, 05C81; Secondary 05A18,03E15.

Key words and phrases. Collatz Conjecture, Syracuse Problem, Hailstone Sequence, Pascal's Triangle and Matrix, Set Theory, Combinatorics, Biased Random Walks, Graph Theory, Dyck Paths.

Honorary Authorship to my wife, Nina, who endured many years and countless hours watching me chase and finally catch the rabbit in the "Year of the Rabbit". While the final drafting of the paper "dragged on" to end of the "Year of the Dragon", she ensured I didn't spend too much time down the rabbit-hole, listened to me "explain" the "patterns" and generally kept me sane.

1. THE COLLATZ CONJECTURE

1.1. The Conjecture.

The Collatz Conjecture has two potential operations or steps. For all positive integers, if integer $n_{(i-1)}$ is *Even* then $n_i = n_{(i-1)}/2$. If integer $n_{(i-1)}$ is *Odd* then $n_i = (3 * n_{(i-1)} + 1)$. The conjecture is that, when applied recursively, eventually, all positive starting integers will result in a terminal periodic sequence of (1, 2, 4) of period 3.

The Short-cut function of the Collatz Conjecture, which is used in this paper, also has two potential operations or steps. For all positive integers, if integer $n_{(i-1)}$ is *Even* then $n_i = n_{(i-1)}/2$. If integer $n_{(i-1)}$ is *Odd* then $n_i = (3 * n_{(i-1)} + 1)/2$. The conjecture is that, when applied recursively, eventually, all positive starting integers will result in a terminal periodic sequence of (1, 2) of period 2.

1.2. A Brief History and Background.

The Collatz Conjecture has been neither proved nor disproved since first introduced in 1937 by Lothar Collatz.

Since then, much has been written about this famous unproven conjecture in academic journals, mainstream media and on social media by professional mathematicians, journalists and amateurs. In addition, with the advent of social media, there are now literally hundreds, if not thousands, of videos and podcasts purporting to fully explain or prove the conjecture.

This paper will not attempt to provide a history of all the research and documentation available. Somewhere in this documentary chaos, it is possible, maybe even probable, that a proof, predating this proof, already exists.¹

The bibliography will only list those references that are cited in the paper, that the author found used methods or provided insights that were either similar to those used by the author to prove the conjecture or provided some historical guidance.

The two (2) sentences, listed below, which can be extracted from the Wikipedia Collatz Conjecture article, are often repeated verbatim in papers, and other media, on the Conjecture, almost as an pre-loaded excuse if a proof is found incomplete, while ignoring the “weasel words”. Alternatively, many authors may include these sentences to emphasize that they alone were able to prove the conjecture while the mathematical greats could not. I do neither. Rather I submit my proof humbly, more as “a blind hog [that] has by chance found an acorn”² [1], planted it, watered it and finally grew a beautiful tree that bore fruit. I only ask you to sample the fruit and see if it is agreeable to you.

- (1) “Paul Erdős said about the Collatz conjecture: ‘Mathematics **may** not be ready for such problems [Bold added].’ ” [2][3].
- (2) “Jeffrey Lagarias stated in 2010 that the Collatz conjecture ‘is an extraordinarily difficult problem, completely out of reach of present day mathematics’ ” [2].

¹Infinite Monkey Theorem (second Borel–Cantelli lemma) - With infinite monkeys typing for infinity, one may type a *proof* but, if all the monkeys (including the author) are busy typing, with no time to read...

²Complete quote - “Spiegelberg, thou art a great man! or else a blind hog has by chance found an acorn.”

- This was an incomplete quote which seems to state that a proof is currently absolutely impossible. The full quote, however, is:
 - “The track record on the $3x + 1$ problem so far **suggests** that this is an extraordinarily difficult problem, completely out of reach of present day mathematics [Bold added]” [4].

Beginning in 2014, Dr. Mike Winkler pre-published a series of three (3) papers.[5][6][7] The third paper was updated in 2024 with the title “The Recursive Stopping Time Structure of the $3x + 1$ Function”. In his papers, Dr. Winkler presents algorithms and resulting data structures that are created in a “pascal-like” manner. In Dr. Winkler’s third paper, the table “Table 1: Triangle expansion of the number of congruences (mod $2k$)” contains identical internal data (up to Step 11) to that found in this paper, in the table, “Table 3: Pascal-like Unsolved Numerators of Reduced Fractional ($UN_{L_{Step_i}}$)%”. Although the internal data in both tables is identical, the data is generated using different methods. The data and results in this paper were arrived at independently. Dr. Winkler’s papers were initially found while searching OEIS.org for the sequence (1, 1, 1, 2, 3, 4, 8, 13, 19, 38, 64, 128, 226, 367 . . .) [OEIS A076227][8].

Although there may be other papers existing, Dr. Winkler’s work was the earliest found that identified this “pascal-like” behavior in the unsolved sub-sequences of the Collatz. Dr. Winkler’s work and this work are very similar in their approach and initial results. Dr. Winkler used modular arithmetic and congruence classes, whereas this paper uses unsolved sub-sets and algebra to prove the same results. Although different in method, the two approaches are equivalent.

Dr. Winkler’s states in his conclusion of the third paper, “Up to this point, our results on the congruences . . . are absolutely precise and clear. These results are given without the use of any statistical and probability theoretical methods. . . . from this point, statistical and probability theoretical methods ³ could be used to show that the congruences . . . build the set of the natural numbers.[7]”

There is a high degree of confidence that the theorems and proofs presented in this paper do what Dr. Winkler suggested and prove that the Collatz Conjecture is true for all positive starting integers.

In 2019, Professor Terence Tao pre-published his first version of a paper containing a proof that the conjecture is true for “almost all” positive integers titled “Almost all orbits of the Collatz map attain almost bounded values”[9]. His final version was published in 2022. A 2019 article in Quanta Magazine, regarding his initial version of the proof, stated “It is arguably the strongest result in the long history of the conjecture . . . Tao’s method is almost certainly incapable of getting all the way to a full proof of the Collatz conjecture”[10] .

Professor Tao used only a finite subset of the infinite Natural Number set (\mathbb{N}_1), which, although carefully selected in a brilliant but complicated manner, is still only a sampling of the possibilities, so his conclusion must be “Almost all . . .”.

The Quanta Magazine article attempts to simplify the sample selection criteria, “For example, Tao’s starting sample is weighted to contain no multiples of 3, since the Collatz process quickly weeds out multiples of 3 anyway. Some of the other weights Tao came up with are more complicated. He weights his starting sample

³As will be shown in this proof, although some statistical and probability theoretical *methods* will be used, once the Exactable nature of the Collatz is proved, Probability becomes Exactability.

toward numbers that have a remainder of 1 after being divided by 3, and away from numbers that have a remainder of 2 after being divided by 3.[10]”

One method of disproving the conjecture is to find at least one positive integer for which the conjecture does not hold true. This has been, and is being, attempted using many different computer programs. This is basically a “brute force” method, although many of the attempts include some very sophisticated and complex logic, as well as distributed computing, to speed the process. To date, no counter-example has been found and the conjecture has been verified for all starting values up to “ $2^{68} \approx 2.95 \times 10^{20}$ ” [11]. This computer evidence is still not a rigorous proof.

2. OUTLINE OF THE THEOREMS AND PROOFS PRESENTED

The one and, most likely, only method of proving that the conjecture is true, is to prove that for all positive starting integers ($n_{Original} = n_O$) there must exist a $Step_i$, after which, either $n_i < n_O$ or $n_i = 1$ (or both, in the case of $n_O = 2$). This must be proven for infinite⁴ positive starting integers, not just a finite sub-set.

As previously stated, there is a high degree of confidence that the theorems and proofs presented in this paper do exactly this and therefore prove that the Collatz Conjecture is true for all positive starting integers.

The following are brief and basic descriptions of the theorems, proofs and some of the other definitions and functions used in the proofs.

2.1. Equally partitioned INFINITE Sub-sets (I_j) of \mathbb{N}_1 .

The infinite set \mathbb{N}_1 with cardinality \aleph_0 can be equally partitioned infinitely into 2^x smaller and smaller INFINITE sub-sets $I_j \in \{I_1, I_2, I_3, \dots, I_{2^x}\}$, where $x \in \mathbb{N}_0$.

$$I_j = \{n \mid j + m * 2^x, \text{ where } x \in \mathbb{N}_0, \\ m \in \{0, 1, 2, \dots, 2^z - 1\}, \\ \text{and } z = \infty \text{ (for infinite sub-sets)}\}$$

2.2. Unequally partitioned FINITE Sub-sets (F_j) of \mathbb{N}_1 .

The infinite set \mathbb{N}_1 can also be unequally partitioned infinitely into FINITE sub-sets $F_j \in \{F_0, F_1, F_2, \dots, F_\infty\}$

$$F_j = \begin{cases} \{n \mid n = 1\} & \text{if } j = 0 \\ \{n \mid 2^{j-1} + 1 \leq n \leq 2^j\} & \text{if } j \geq 1 \end{cases}$$

2.3. Identical and Alternating Equivalence Parity Theorem.

It will be proven that recursively applying the Short-Cut Collatz Function to all members of any sub-set (I_j), where $x \in \mathbb{N}_0$, will result in an exactly identical parity sequence up to and including $Step_x$ that are unique to that sub-set.

It will be proven that the Short-cut Collatz function is a pure binomial expansion. Provided that the sample size is 2^{x+z} ($z \in \mathbb{N}_0$) sequential members of a sub-set (I_j), where $x \in \mathbb{N}_0$, then after the Identical Parity Sequence ending after $Step_x$, for every future step up to and including $Step_{x+z}$, of the resulting n_i , exactly 50% will be

⁴In this paper, infinite and infinity (∞) mean Actual/Completed versus Potential

Even and exactly 50% will be *Odd*. Immediately after Step_x , the parity of n_i for each sequential member of the sub-set will alternate.⁵

It will be proven that the Short-cut Collatz function, when applied to sub-set (I_1) of cardinality \aleph_0 , (\aleph_1) will produce, starting at Step_0 , a complete ‘‘Pascal’s Triangle’’ of the Numerators of the Reduced Fractional % Distribution Results at each potential $\frac{\text{Even}}{\text{Odd}}$ step ratio for each Step_i from Step_0 to Step_∞ .

2.4. $\frac{\text{Even}}{\text{Odd}}$ step ratio $> \log_2(3) - 1$ Theorem.

It will be proven that for every $n_O \in \aleph_1$, the first time there exists a Step_i in the Shortcut Collatz Function where $\frac{\text{Even}}{\text{Odd}}$ step ratio $> \log_2(3) - 1$ then $n_i \leq n_O$.

2.5. No Terminal Loop Sequence other than $\{1, 2, 1, 2, \dots \infty\}$ Theorem.

It will be proven that there are no terminal loop sequences possible other than the known terminal loop sequence $\{1, 2, 1, 2, \dots \infty\}$.

2.6. *Even Steps* $\geq \log_2(n_O) + \text{Odd Steps} * (\log_2(3) - 1)$ Theorem.

It will be proven that for every $n_O \in \aleph_1$, the first time there exists a Step_i in the Shortcut Collatz Function where, *Even Steps* $\geq \log_2(n_O) + \text{Odd Steps} * (\log_2(3) - 1)$ then $n_i = 1$.

2.7. Weighted Arithmetic Mean and Percentage of Unproven Sub-sets.

With each additional iteration, as $i \rightarrow \infty$, the Weighted Arithmetic Mean of the Unsolved $\frac{\text{Even}}{\text{Odd}}$ step ratios approaches an upper limit of $\log_2(3) - 1$ and the percentage of unproven Sub-sets (integers) approaches a lower limit of zero (0). Neither will reach it’s limit, since infinity is forever. These limits will be used as an additional proof that, where $n_O \in \{1, 2, 3, \dots 2^{x \leq \infty}\}$, inevitably, $n_i < n_O$ and that, also inevitably, $n_i = 1$.

2.8. Cumulative Probability and Exactability Distribution Curves.

When the Proof Lines for $n_i \leq n_O$ and $n_i = 1$ are plotted against the Cumulative (Pascal) Probability Distribution Curves, it will be conservatively proven that there will always be an intersection point for any Probability Distribution % is calculated.

Still conservative, but more exact, Cumulative (Pascal-like) Exactability Distribution Curves, based on the Pascal-like calculations of the fraction of unsolved Sub-sets (sequences) that end at each Energy Level for each Step_i will be proven to have an *earlier* intersection point with the Proof Line for $n_i \leq n_O$ than a Cumulative (Pascal) Probability Distribution Curves with the same Probability Distribution % calculated. The Exactable curves stop at the Proof Line for $n_i \leq n_O$.

2.9. Reductio Ad Absurdum Collatz Conjecture Theorem.

By the previous proofs and an extreme reductio ad absurdum example, it will be proved that the Collatz Conjecture is true.

⁵Alternating parities will only occur after Step_x . Sub-set must then be continuously equally partitioned again before each Step_{xPlus} for continuity of alternating parities after each Step_{xPlus} .

3. EMPIRICAL METHODOLOGY AND RESULTS WITH TABLES AND FIGURES

Plotting the Short-cut Collatz function sequences where the y -axis is the $\frac{Even}{Odd}$ step ratio and the x -axis is the number of *All* steps provides some clarity to the function but remains slightly chaotic and hard to intuitively follow. (Figure 1)

Plotting the sequences where the y -axis is the number of *Even* steps and the x -axis is the number of *Odd* steps, provides significantly improved observational evidence of the true nature of the Collatz Short-cut function as a pure binomial expansion.⁶ (Table 1, 2, Figures 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7)

Plotting the sequences for every n_O in the sub-set where $n_O \in \{1, 2, 3, \dots, 2^x\}$ up to Step $_{x+z}$ where the value of all $n_i = 1$ (or 2), it is apparent that there are linear limits of the $\frac{Even}{Odd}$ step ratio above which $n_i < n_O$ and $n_i = 1$. For these linear limits, $slope = (\log_2(3) - 1)$. (Figure 4)

Counting the sequences, at each $\frac{Even}{Odd}$ step ratio, for every n_O in the sub-set where $n_O \in \{1, 2, 3, \dots, 2^x\}$, at each Step $_i$, up to and including Step $_x$, dividing by 2^{x-i} , results in reduced fractional % distribution results, with GCD of 2^i , at each particular $\frac{Even}{Odd}$ step ratio for that Step $_i$. The numerators of these fractions form a perfect Pascal's Triangle, up to Step $_x$. (Table 1)

Plotting the sequences for every n_O in the FINITE Sub-set F_x where $n_O \in \{2^{x-1} + 1, 2^{x-1} + 2, 2^{x-1} + 3, \dots, 2^x\}$, up to Step $_{x+z}$, where the value of all $n_i = 1$ (or 2), it is apparent that the y -intercept $\approx \log_2(n_O)$ for the linear upper limits of the $\frac{Even}{Odd}$ step ratio above which $n_{x+z} = 1$ (or 2). (Figure 5)

Plotting the sequences for every n_O in the " z -limited"⁷ INFINITE Sub-set I_1 of cardinality \aleph_0 , $x = 13$ and $z = 13$, where $n_O \in \{1 + 0 * 2^x, 1 + 1 * 2^x, 1 + 2 * 2^x, \dots, 1 + (2^z - 1) * 2^x\}$, up to Step $_{x+z}$, results in an Identical Parity Sequence for all n_O up to Step $_x$, after which a perfect Pascal's Triangle of numerators of the reduced fractional % distribution of the sequences forms, up to Step $_{x+z}$. (Table 1 2, Figures 6 7)

Counting the sequences that have not solved to $n_i < n_O$, at each $\frac{Even}{Odd}$ step ratio, for every n_O in the sub-set where $n_O \in \{1, 2, 3, \dots, 2^x\}$, at each Step $_i$, up to and including Step $_x$, dividing by 2^{x-i} , results in reduced fractional % distribution results, with GCD of 2^i , at each particular $\frac{Even}{Odd}$ step ratio for that Step $_i$. The numerators of these fractions form a Pascal-like Triangle, up to Step $_x$. (Table 3)

Plotting the Weighted Arithmetic Mean of the Unsolved $\frac{Even}{Odd}$ step ratios, using the originally conceived plot, shows that with each additional iteration, as $i \rightarrow \infty$, approaches an upper limit of $\log_2(3) - 1$ and the percentage of unproven integers approaches a lower limit of zero (0). (Figure 8 and Figure 9 Plot 4)

Plotting the Cumulative Probability and Exactability Distribution Curves and the two previously observed linear limits of the $\frac{Even}{Odd}$ step ratio above which $n_i < n_O$ and $n_i = 1$, it is clear that there will always be an intersection point between any probability curve and both limits no matter how low a probability is calculated. The exactability curve always intersects the $n_i < n_O$ limit at an earlier Step than the probability curve of the same percentage. (Tables 4, 5 Figures 9, 10, 11, 12)

It is recommended to print the following Figures and Tables for reference when evaluating the proof.

⁶A 2D (top-down) look at a 3D symmetric matrix where z -axis = The Pascal (or non-symmetric Pascal-like) Matrix Value $_{(at\ xy)}$ or the Partial Diagonal Sum Percentages of the Pascal (or non-symmetric Pascal-like) Matrix Value $_{(at\ xy)}$ (i.e. Folded Cumulative Distribution)

⁷For actual INFINITE Sub-set I_1 , $z = \infty$, for analysis z must be limited.

Originally Conceived Plot with Starting Integer 359

EXACTABILITY VERSUS PROBABILITY

FIGURE 1. Originally Conceived Plot with Starting Integer 359

Reimagined Plot with Starting Integer 359

FIGURE 2. Reimagined Plot with Starting Integer 359

Finite Sub-set Membership Lines with Starting Integer 359

FIGURE 3. Finite Sub-set Membership Lines with Starting Integer 359

Sequence Plots for 16777216 Integers

from $(1 + 0 * 2^0)$ to $(1 + (2^{24} - 1) * 2^0)$
 at intervals of 2^0 for 1000 steps

FIGURE 4. Reimagined Plot of $n \in \{1, 2, 3, \dots, 16777216(2^{24})\}$

TABLE 1. Pascal's Triangle of Numerators of Reduced Fractional ($N_{L_{Step_i}}$) %

Pascal's Triangle of Numerators of Reduced Fractional ($N_{L_{Step_i}}$)% Distribution Results at each Energy Level for Integers $n \in \{1, 2, 3, \dots, 2^x\}$ where $x \geq 13$ from Step 1 to Step 13																
ENERGY LEVEL (EL) = q = <i>EVEN</i> STEPS																
STEP _i	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	GCD(2^i)	≈ % < <i>EEV</i>
0	1														2^0	100
1	1	1													2^1	50
2	1	2	1												2^2	25
3	1	3	3	1											2^3	50
4	1	4	6	4	1										2^4	31.25
5	1	5	10	10	5	1									2^5	18.75
6	1	6	15	20	15	6	1								2^6	34.375
7	1	7	21	35	35	21	7	1							2^7	≈22.656
8	1	8	28	56	70	56	28	8	1						2^8	≈14.453
9	1	9	36	84	126	126	84	36	9	1					2^9	≈25.391
10	1	10	45	120	210	252	210	120	45	10	1				2^{10}	≈17.188
11	1	11	55	165	330	462	462	330	165	55	11	1			2^{11}	≈27.441
12	1	12	66	220	495	792	924	792	495	220	66	12	1		2^{12}	≈19.385
13	1	13	78	286	715	1287	1716	1716	1287	715	286	78	13	1	2^{13}	≈ 13.342

1. Pascal Numbers are the **Numerators of Reduced Fractions** generated by:

$$\frac{N_{L_{Step_i}}}{GCD(2^i)} = \frac{N_{L_{Step_{i-1}}} + N_{(L-1)Step_{i-1}}}{2^{i-1} * 2^1} \text{ where : } L = \text{Number of } EL_L \text{ at Step}_i$$

2. All Integer sequences continued even if $n_i < n_{Original}$ or if $n_i = 1$

3. Bold Larger Numbers are located in *EL*'s, for that Step_i, where $EV < EEV$ and include some Integers that previously had an $EV > EEV$ at an earlier Step_i and $n_{Step_i} < n_{Original}$

4. Where, for each Step_i, $m \in \{0, 1, 2, \dots, 2^{(x-i)} - 1\}$:
 The consistent 1 on left (EL_0) and right (EL_i) sides of the triangle are generated by the Sub-sets: (LEFT) $I_{(j=2^i-1)} \in \{n \mid (2^i - 1) + m * 2^i\}$ and (RIGHT) $I_{(j=2^i)} \in \{n \mid 2^i + m * 2^i\}$

5. Every possible Parity Sequence at Step_i will be followed at least once for a total of 2^i sequences

6. The same distribution occurs starting at Step_x up to Step_{x+z} for any Sub-set where:
 $n_1 \geq 1, n_O \in \{n_1 + 0 * 2^x, n_1 + 1 * 2^x, n_1 + 2 * 2^x, \dots, n_1 + (2^z - 1) * 2^x\}$

Sequence Plots for 16777216 Integers

from ($16777217 + 0 * 2^0$) to ($16777217 + (2^{24} - 1) * 2^0$)
 at intervals of 2^0 for 1000 steps

FIGURE 5. Plot of $n \in \{16777217(2^{24} + 1), 16777218, 16777219, \dots, 33554432(2^{25})\}$

Sequence Plots for 8192 Integers

from $(1 + 0 * 2^{13})$ to $(1 + (2^{13} - 1) * 2^{13})$
 at intervals of 2^{13} for 1000 steps

FIGURE 6. Plot of $n \in \{1, 8193, 16385, \dots, 67100673\}$

ZOOMED Sequence Plots for 8192 Integers

from $(1 + 0 * 2^{13})$ to $(1 + (2^{13} - 1) * 2^{13})$
 at intervals of 2^{13} for 1000 steps

FIGURE 7. ZOOMED Plot of $n \in \{1, 8193, 16385, \dots, 67100673\}$

TABLE 2. Alternating Parity at 417th Step when adding 2⁴¹⁶ to *TI*

Example of Identical and Alternating Parity for 21,407,990,427 tested by adding 2 ⁴¹⁶ to <i>TI</i> from 0 to 9 times and running Collatz for 417 steps Presence of (< <i>n_O</i>) indicates <i>n_i</i> < <i>n_O</i> after previous parity sequence			
First 416 Parity Sequences IDENTICAL for all Integers At < <i>n_O</i> EV ≈ 0.586206896551724 EL = 153	22122221222212211212212221222221222221222211222121 2212211221221122122222222122212111121222121122212 222222221121211222212222212222222212121211112221 221122111222122222221212222221121122221222212212 22122212112211122222211112211221212212222212221 21122121112221122222121122112222211112212222112 22112221222222221122112222121222212112121122222 2212111222121221122112212212121222122112121212211 21122121122111(< <i>n_O</i>)11		
Integer (<i>n_{Original}</i>)	417th Parity	Integer (<i>n_{Original}</i>)	417th Parity
<i>TI</i> = 21,407,990,427	2	169,230,328,010,303,641,331, 690,318,856,389,386,196,071, 590,247,882,556,495,704,531, 248,437,872,567,112,920,983, 350,278,406,001,133,879,963	1
338,460,656,020,607,282,663, 380,637,712,778,772,392,143, 180,495,765,112,991,409,062, 496,875,745,134,225,841,966, 700,556,811,980,859,769,499	2	507,690,984,030,910,923,995, 070,956,569,168,158,588,214, 770,743,647,669,487,113,593, 745,313,617,701,338,762,950, 050,835,217,960,585,659,035	1
676,921,312,041,214,565,326, 761,275,425,557,544,784,286, 360,991,530,225,982,818,124, 993,751,490,268,451,683,933, 401,113,623,940,311,548,571	2	846,151,640,051,518,206,658, 451,594,281,946,930,980,357, 951,239,412,782,478,522,656, 242,189,362,835,564,604,916, 751,392,029,920,037,438,107	1
1,015,381,968,061,821,847, 990,141,913,138,336,317,176, 549,541,487,295,338,974,227, 187,490,627,235,402,677,525, 900,101,670,435,899,763,327, 643	2	1,184,612,296,072,125,489, 321,832,231,994,725,703,372, 641,131,735,177,895,469,931, 718,739,065,107,969,790,446, 883,451,948,841,879,489,217, 179	1
1,353,842,624,082,429,130, 653,522,550,851,115,089,568, 732,721,983,060,451,965,636, 249,987,502,980,536,903,367, 866,802,227,247,859,215,106, 715	2	1,523,072,952,092,732,771, 985,212,869,707,504,475,764, 824,312,230,943,008,461,340, 781,235,940,853,104,016,288, 850,152,505,653,838,940,996, 251	1

TABLE 3. Pascal-like Unsolved Numerators of Reduced Fractional $(UN_{L_{Step_i}})\%$

Pascal-like Triangle of Unsolved Numerators of Reduced Fractional $(UN)\%$ Distribution Results at each Energy Level for Integers $n \in \{1, 2, 3, \dots, 2^x\}$ where $x \geq 13$ from Step 1 to Step 24 ... 58														
STEP _i	ENERGY LEVEL								EEL	AST (A) or UST (U)	Total Unsolved	Percent Unsolved	GCD	
	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7						8
0	1									-	-	1	100	2 ⁰
1	1									1	A	1	50	2 ¹
2	1									1	A	1	25	2 ²
3	1	1								2	U	2	25	2 ³
4	1	2								2	A	3	18.8	2 ⁴
5	1	3								2	A	4	12.5	2 ⁵
6	1	4	3							3	U	8	12.5	2 ⁶
7	1	5	7							3	A	13	10.2	2 ⁷
8	1	6	12							3	A	19	7.42	2 ⁸
9	1	7	18	12						4	U	38	7.42	2 ⁹
10	1	8	25	30						4	A	64	6.25	2 ¹⁰
11	1	9	33	55	30					5	U	128	6.25	2 ¹¹
12	1	10	42	88	85					5	A	226	5.52	2 ¹²
13	1	11	52	130	173					5	A	367	4.48	2 ¹³
14	1	12	63	182	303	173				6	U	734	4.48	2 ¹⁴
15	1	13	75	245	485	476				6	A	1295	3.95	2 ¹⁵
16	1	14	88	320	730	961				6	A	2114	3.23	2 ¹⁶
17	1	15	102	408	1050	1691	961			7	U	4228	3.23	2 ¹⁷
18	1	16	117	510	1458	2741	2652			7	A	7495	2.86	2 ¹⁸
19	1	17	133	627	1968	4199	5393	2652		8	U	14990	2.76	2 ¹⁹
20	1	18	150	760	2595	6167	9592	8045		8	A	27328	2.61	2 ²⁰
21	1	19	168	910	3355	8762	15759	17637		8	A	46611	2.22	2 ²¹
22	1	20	187	1078	4265	12117	24521	33396	17637	9	U	93222	2.22	2 ²²
23	1	21	207	1265	5343	16382	36638	57917	51033	9	A	168807	2.01	2 ²³
24	1	22	228	1472	6608	21725	53020	94555	108950	9	A	286581	1.71	2 ²⁴
⋮	⋮	⋮	⋮	⋮	⋮	⋮	⋮	⋮	⋮	⋮	⋮	⋮	⋮	⋮
⋮	⋮	⋮	⋮	⋮	⋮	⋮	⋮	⋮	⋮	⋮	⋮	⋮	⋮	⋮
58	1	56	1,537	27,550	362,588	3,735,069	31,347,470	220,302,576	1,322,261,748	EEL = 34 and AST	615,588,850,887,706	0.21	2 ⁵⁸	

45 degree rotations on Step 22, 23 and 24 and Multi-lines on Step 58 to make table fit page

Pascal-like Numbers are the **Unsolved Numerators of Reduced Fractions** generated by:

$$f\left(\frac{UN_{L_{Step(i)}}}{GCD(2^i)}\right) = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{if } L \geq EEL_{Step_i} \\ \frac{UN_{L_{Step(i-1)}} + UN_{(L-1)_{Step(i-1)}}}{2^{i-1} * 2^1} & \text{if } L < EEL_{Step_i} \end{cases}$$

where : L = Number of EL_L at Step_i

AST (A) = Allowable Stopping Time
 UST (U) = Unallowable Stopping Time
 EEL = Escape Energy Level = $ceiling(i - i * \log_3(2))$
 All Integer sequences STOPPED AND NOT COUNTED if:
 $n_i < n_{Original}$ or if $n_i = 1$
 At each Step_i, every potential UNSOLVED Parity Sequence up to that Step_i has been used at least once.
 Total Unsolved at each Step_i matches exactly with OEIS - A076227 Number of surviving Collatz residues mod 2^n [8].

FIGURE 8. Weighted Arithmetic Mean up to Step 456

TABLE 4. Pascal Matrix Folded Cumulative Probability and Conservative 10% Points

STEP 1. Pascal's Matrix														
13	1	14	105	560	2380	8568	27132	77520	203490	497420	1144066	2496144	5200300	10400600
12	1	13	91	455	1820	6188	18564	50388	125970	293930	646646	1352078	2704156	5200300
11	1	12	78	364	1365	4368	12376	31824	75582	167960	352716	705432	1352078	2496144
10	1	11	66	286	1001	3003	8008	19448	43758	92378	184756	352716	646646	1144066
9	1	10	55	220	715	2002	5005	11440	24310	48620	92378	167960	293930	497420
8	1	9	45	165	495	1287	3003	6435	12870	24310	43758	75582	125970	203490
7	1	8	36	120	330	792	1716	3432	6435	11440	19448	31824	50388	77520
6	1	7	28	84	210	462	924	1716	3003	5005	8008	12376	18564	27132
5	1	6	21	56	126	252	462	792	1287	2002	3003	4368	6188	8568
4	1	5	15	35	70	126	210	330	495	715	1001	1365	1820	2380
3	1	4	10	20	35	56	84	120	165	220	286	364	455	560
2	1	3	6	10	15	21	28	36	45	55	66	78	91	105
1	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14
0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
STEP 2. Partial Diagonal Sum's (from Top Left and Bottom Right toward Center) (Folded)														
13	1	15	121	697	3214	12616	43796	137980	401930	1097790	2842226	7036530	16777216	38754732
12	1	14	106	576	2517	9402	31180	94184	263950	695860	1744436	4194304	9740686	16777216
11	1	13	92	470	1941	6885	21778	63004	169766	431910	1048576	2449868	4194304	7036530
10	1	12	79	378	1471	4944	14893	41226	106762	262144	616666	1048576	1744436	2842226
9	1	11	67	299	1093	3473	9949	26333	65536	155382	262144	431910	695860	1097790
8	1	10	56	232	794	2380	6476	16384	39203	65536	106762	169766	263950	401930
7	1	9	46	176	562	1586	4096	9908	16384	26333	41226	63004	94184	137980
6	1	8	37	130	386	1024	2510	4096	6476	9949	14893	21778	31180	43796
5	1	7	29	93	256	638	1024	1586	2380	3473	4944	6885	9402	12616
4	1	6	22	64	163	256	386	562	794	1093	1471	1941	2517	3214
3	1	5	16	42	64	93	130	176	232	299	378	470	576	697
2	1	4	11	16	22	29	37	46	56	67	79	92	106	121
1	1	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15
0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
STEP 3. Partial Diagonal Sum \approx % (Folded)														
Numbers with Arrows are Conservative Plot Points for $\approx 10\%$ Probability Curve														
13	0.01	0.09	0.37	1.06	2.45	4.81	8.35	13.2	19.2	26.2	33.9	41.9	50.0	57.7
12	0.02	0.17	0.65	1.76	3.84	7.17	11.9	18.0	25.2	33.2	41.6	50.0	58.1	50.0
11	0.05	0.32	1.12	2.87	5.92	10.5	16.6	24.0	32.4	41.2	50.0	58.4	50.0	41.9
10	0.10	0.59	1.93	4.61	8.98	15.1	22.7	31.5	40.7	50.0	58.8	50.0	41.6	33.9
9	0.20	1.07	3.27	7.30	13.3	21.2	30.4	40.2	50.0	59.3	50.0	41.2	33.2	26.2
8	0.39	1.95	5.47	11.3	19.4	29.1	39.5	50.0	59.8	50.0	40.7	32.4	25.2	19.2
7	0.78	3.52	8.98	17.2	27.4	38.7	50.0	60.5	50.0	40.2	31.5	24.0	18.0	13.2
6	1.56	6.25	14.5	25.4	37.7	50.0	61.3	50.0	39.5	30.4	22.7	16.6	11.9	8.35 \rightarrow
5	3.13	10.9	22.7	36.3	50.0	62.3	50.0	38.7	29.1	21.2	15.1	10.5	7.17 \rightarrow	4.81 \uparrow
4	6.25	18.8	34.4	50.0	63.7	50.0	37.7	27.4	19.4	13.3	8.98 \rightarrow	5.92 \rightarrow	3.84 \uparrow	2.45
3	12.50	31.3	50.0	65.6	50.0	36.3	25.4	17.2	11.3	7.30 \rightarrow	4.61 \uparrow	2.87	1.76	1.06
2	25.0	50.0	68.8	50.0	34.4	22.7	14.5	8.98 \rightarrow	5.47 \rightarrow	3.27 \uparrow	1.93	1.12	0.65	0.37
1	50.0	75.0	50.0	31.3	18.8	10.9	6.25 \rightarrow	3.52 \uparrow	1.95	1.07	0.59	0.32	0.17	0.09
0	100.0 \rightarrow	50.0 \rightarrow	25.0 \rightarrow	12.5 \rightarrow	6.25 \rightarrow	3.13 \rightarrow	1.56 \uparrow	0.78	0.39	0.20	0.10	0.05	0.02	0.01
	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13

Odd Steps

3d Folded Cumulative Probability using matrix data from Table 4 Step 3

Peak Folded Cumulative % Probability starts to decrease, flatten and widen as Steps increase from 100% at Step 0 ([x,y,z] = [0,0,100]) to ≈ 57.7% at Step 26 ([x,y,z] = [13,13,57.7]).
 As Steps increase to infinity the Peak Folded Cumulative % Probability will approach but will never reach the limit of 50%.

PLOT 1: 0° Angle and 90° Elevation

Includes ≈ 50%, 40%, 30%, 20% and 10% Probability Curve Contour Lines
 2 Outer Contour Curves are ≈ 10% (See Data in Table 4 Step 3)

PLOT 3: ≈ -59.674° Angle and 30° Elevation
 = -59.674° is = 180°/π * atan (log_e(3) - 1) - 90°

PLOT 2: -45° Angle and 30° Elevation

3 views of $n_i=1$ limit for $n_{original} \leq 2^4$

Upper Straight Line on Plot 1 from [0,4] to [13,11.6]

Upper Left Black Grid on Plot 2 from [0,4,0] to [13,11.6,100]

Left Straight Line on Plot 3 from [0,4,0] to [13, 11.6,100]

4 views of $n_i < n_{original}$ limit

Lower Straight Line on Plot 1 from [0,0] to [13,7.6]

Lower Right Black Grid on Plot 2 from [0,0,0] to [13,7.6,100]

Right Straight Line on Plot 3 from [0,0,0] to [13,7.6,100]

2 Black "curves" of actual cumulative % below limit on Plot 4 (Exactable and Probable)

PLOT 4: +45° Angle and 0° Elevation

FIGURE 9. Example 3D Views of Folded Cumulative Probability Distribution and Percent Curves

FIGURE 10. Folded Cumulative Probability Distribution Percent Curves

$1/2^{13}$, $1/2^{26}$, $1/2^{31.5}$ and $1/2^{44}$ %
 Sample Cumulative Exactability Percent Curves

FIGURE 11. Sample Cumulative Exactability Distribution Percent Curves

FIGURE 12. Cumulative Exactability versus Probability Distribution Percent Curves

4. SUPPORTING TERMS, DEFINITIONS, FUNCTIONS AND EQUATIONS

The following supporting terms, definitions, descriptions, constants, variables, functions and equations, most of which are crucial to the understanding and proof of the Collatz Conjecture, are reviewed, revised or introduced in this section. For most of the new or revised equations, their validity is readily apparent. For those that require an in-depth proof, it will be provided in associated theorem sections. Many of the terms and equations are referenced in the previous supporting figures and tables.

4.1. Conventional Binary & New Binary and Ternary Collatz Functions.

4.1.1. Conventional (Binary) Parity Original Collatz Function.

$$(4.1) \quad f(n_i) = \begin{cases} \frac{n_{(i-1)}}{2} & \text{if } n_{(i-1)} \equiv 0 \pmod{2} \\ & \text{(Add 0 to end of **Parity** Sequence)} \\ 3n_{(i-1)} + 1 & \text{if } n_{(i-1)} \equiv 1 \pmod{2} \\ & \text{(Add 1 to end of **Parity** Sequence)} \end{cases}$$

This is the function as originally formulated and captures each individual step in a *Parity* Sequence where according to the conventional definition of *Parity*, steps resulting from *Even* integers are assigned a *Parity* = 0 and steps resulting from *Odd* integers are assigned a *Parity* = 1. Not used in this proof beyond this definition.

4.1.2. Conventional (Binary) Parity Short-cut Collatz Function.

$$(4.2) \quad f(n_i) = \begin{cases} \frac{n_{(i-1)}}{2} & \text{if } n_{(i-1)} \equiv 0 \pmod{2} \\ & \text{(Add 0 to end of **Parity** Sequence)} \\ \frac{3n_{(i-1)}+1}{2} & \text{if } n_{(i-1)} \equiv 1 \pmod{2} \\ & \text{(Add 1 to end of **Parity** Sequence)} \end{cases}$$

A condensed function which accounts for the fact that $3n + 1$ is *Even* whenever n is *Odd* and must be followed by an *Even* function. This function yields smaller values for the Stopping Time and Total Stopping Time without changing the overall dynamics of the process. Not used in this proof beyond this definition.

4.1.3. New (Binary) Parity Short-cut Collatz Function.

$$(4.3) \quad f(n_i) = \begin{cases} \frac{3^0 n_{(i-1)}}{2^1} + \frac{(2^0-1)}{2^1} & \text{if } n_{(i-1)} \equiv 0 \pmod{2} \\ & \text{(Add 0 to end of **Parity** Sequence)} \\ \frac{3^1 n_{(i-1)}}{2^1} + \frac{(2^1-1)}{2^1} & \text{if } n_{(i-1)} \equiv 1 \pmod{2} \\ & \text{(Add 1 to end of **Parity** Sequence)} \end{cases}$$

A modification, by the author, of the Conventional (*Binary*) *Parity* Short-cut Collatz Function using equivalent function equations. These equivalent equations, are critical for the proof.

4.1.4. *New (Ternary) Parity Short-cut Collatz Function.*

$$(4.4) \quad f(n_i) = \begin{cases} \frac{3^0 n_{(i-1)}}{2^1} + \frac{(2^0-1)}{2^1} & \text{if } n_{(i-1)} \equiv 0 \pmod{2} \\ & \text{(Add 1 to end of **Parity** Sequence)} \\ \frac{3^1 n_{(i-1)}}{2^1} + \frac{(2^1-1)}{2^1} & \text{if } n_{(i-1)} \equiv 1 \pmod{2} \\ & \text{(Add 2 to end of **Parity** Sequence)} \end{cases}$$

Modification of the New (*Binary*) *Parity* Short-cut Collatz Function, where, using the *Ternary* Numbering System, each result is assigned a *Parity* = (1, 2) versus *Parity* = (0, 1). Steps resulting from *Even* integers are assigned a *Parity* = 1 and steps resulting from *Odd* integers are assigned a *Parity* = 2. Use of the *Ternary* Number System is not critical for the proof but is beneficial because it visually reflects the number of Original Collatz Function Steps performed at each Short-Cut Collatz Function step and it allows for use of the *Ternarity* Short-Cut Function described below.

This version of the Short-cut Collatz Function will be the one utilized.

4.1.5. *New (Ternary) Ternarity Short-cut Collatz Function.*

$$(4.5) \quad f(n_i) = \begin{cases} n_{(i-1)} & \text{if } n_{(i-1)} < n_O \text{ (or } n_{(i-1)} = 1) \\ & \text{(Add 0 to end of **Ternarity** Sequence)} \\ & \text{(Or alternatively - STOP the function)} \\ \frac{3^0 n_{(i-1)}}{2^1} + \frac{(2^0-1)}{2^1} & \text{if } n_{(i-1)} \equiv 0 \pmod{2} \\ & \text{(Add 1 to end of **Ternarity** Sequence)} \\ \frac{3^1 n_{(i-1)}}{2^1} + \frac{(2^1-1)}{2^1} & \text{if } n_{(i-1)} \equiv 1 \pmod{2} \\ & \text{(Add 2 to end of **Ternarity** Sequence)} \end{cases}$$

Further modification of the New Short-cut (*Binary*) Collatz Function, where, using the *Ternary* Numbering System, each result is assigned a *Ternarity* = (0, 1, 2). Steps resulting from *Even* integers are assigned a *Ternarity* = 1 and steps resulting from *Odd* integers are assigned a *Ternarity* = 2. However, once $n_{(i-1)} < n_{Original}$ (or $n_{(i-1)} = 1$), it is assigned a *Ternarity* = 0 and all following Steps will also result in a *Ternarity* = 0. This “traps” the Energy Value which is defined later or stops the function, at the first result where $n_{(i-1)} < n_O$ (or $n_{(i-1)} = 1$).

This version of the Short-cut Collatz Function will not be utilized in the proof and is included only for completeness since it represents the point at which many other attempted proofs stop (i.e. When $n_{(i-1)} < n_O$). A representation of this version is included in the Originally Conceived Plot (Figure 1).

It became apparent that when evaluating any Sub-set I_j of \mathbb{N}_1 , that the Short-cut Collatz Function must be recursively applied to all $n_O \in I_j$ beyond the Step where $n_{(i-1)} < n_O$ and then continued beyond the Step where $n_{(i-1)} = 1$ until all $n_O \in I_j$ reach a Step where $n_{(i-1)} = 1$ (or 2) to determine the true nature of the Function.

The term *Ternarity*, as used in this paper, is not meant to imply any (mod 3) equivalence. It is only used for clarity to differentiate between a *Parity* sequence based on the *Binary* Numbering System and a new sequence based on the *Ternary* Numbering System.

Use of the term *Ternarity* in previously published papers appears to be concentrated mainly in the field of linguistics and it is not the author's intent to co-opt the term.

4.2. Stopping Time & Total Stopping Time (*ST* & *TST*).

Stopping Time, also referred to as “dropping time”, is the number of Steps (i) required for n_O to reach a value where $f(n_O)_{\text{Step}_i} < n_O$. Total Stopping Time is the number of Steps (i) required for n_O to reach $f(n_O)_{\text{Step}_i} = 1$ the first time. The Short-cut Collatz Function yields smaller values for the Stopping Time and Total Stopping Time without changing the overall dynamics of the process. The New (Ternary) *Ternarity* Short-cut Collatz Function, except $n_O = 1$ or 2 , will only result in a Stopping Time since the function essentially stops once the Stopping Time is reached.

4.3. Allowable & Unallowable Stopping Times (*AST* & *UST*).

$$(4.6) \quad AST(n) = \lfloor 1 + n * \log_2(3) \rfloor \quad \text{where : } n \in \mathbb{N}_0$$

$$(4.7) \quad UST(n) = \left\lceil \frac{n}{1 - \log_3(2)} \right\rceil \quad \text{where : } n \in \mathbb{N}_0$$

The equation, $a(n) = \lfloor 1 + n * \log(3) / \log(2) \rfloor$, appears to have been first connected with the Collatz Conjecture by K. Spage on October 22, 2009. To quote:

“This sequence represents allowable values of the ‘dropping time’ in the Collatz ($3x+1$) problem when iterated according to the function $f(n) := n/2$ if n is even, $(3n+1)/2$ otherwise, as tabulated in A126241. There is one exception, A126241(1), which has been set to zero by convention. - K. Spage, Oct 22 2009” [12]

The equation, derived by the author, $u(n) = \lceil n / (1 - \log(2) / \log(3)) \rceil$ generates a sequence that is the exact compliment to A020914. The sequence then represents the Unallowable values of the Stopping Time (dropping time) in the Collatz ($3x+1$) problem when iterated using a Short-cut Collatz Function. Although not used directly in this proof, the equations for *AST* and *UST* can be used to derive the equations for Total Solved & Unsolved Energy Levels at Step $_i$ (*TSEL* & *TUEL*) below. Hereafter, this proof will use the $\log_z(y)$ versus $\log(y) / \log(z)$ form.

4.4. Equally partitioned INFINITE Sub-sets (I_j) of \mathbb{N}_1 .

$$(4.8) \quad I_j \in \{I_1, I_2, I_3, \dots, I_{2^x}\} \quad \text{where } x \in \mathbb{N}_0$$

$$(4.9) \quad \begin{aligned} I_j &= \{n \mid j + m * 2^x, \text{ where } x \in \mathbb{N}_0, \\ &\quad m \in \{0, 1, 2, \dots, 2^z - 1\}, \\ &\quad \text{and } z = \infty \text{ (for infinite sub-sets)} \\ &\quad \text{or } z \in \mathbb{N}_0 \text{ (to limit sub-sets for analysis)} \} \end{aligned}$$

The infinite set \mathbb{N}_1 with cardinality \aleph_0 can be equally partitioned infinitely into 2^x , smaller and smaller, infinite sub-sets $I_j \in \{I_1, I_2, I_3, \dots, I_{2^x}\}$, where $x \in \mathbb{N}_0$.

Example 4.1. INFINITE Sub-sets where $x = 2$.

$$I_1 = \{1 + 0 * 2^2, 1 + 1 * 2^2, 1 + 2 * 2^2 \dots 1 + (2^\infty - 1) * 2^2\}$$

$$I_1 = \{1, 5, 9 \dots 1 + (2^\infty - 1) * 2^2\}$$

$$I_2 = \{2 + 0 * 2^2, 2 + 1 * 2^2, 2 + 2 * 2^2 \dots 2 + (2^\infty - 1) * 2^2\}$$

$$I_2 = \{2, 6, 10 \dots 2 + (2^\infty - 1) * 2^2\}$$

$$I_3 = \{3 + 0 * 2^2, 3 + 1 * 2^2, 3 + 2 * 2^2 \dots 3 + (2^\infty - 1) * 2^2\}$$

$$I_3 = \{3, 7, 11 \dots 3 + (2^\infty - 1) * 2^2\}$$

$$I_4 = \{4 + 0 * 2^2, 4 + 1 * 2^2, 4 + 2 * 2^2 \dots 4 + (2^\infty - 1) * 2^2\}$$

$$I_4 = \{4, 8, 12 \dots 4 + (2^\infty - 1) * 2^2\}$$

$$\therefore I_1 \cup I_2 \cup I_3 \cup I_4 = \mathbb{N}_1$$

$$\therefore |I_1| = |I_2| = |I_3| = |I_4|$$

$$\therefore |I_1| + |I_2| + |I_3| + |I_4| = |\mathbb{N}_1| = \infty$$

Example 4.2. Partition \mathbf{I}_3 where $x = 2$ to \mathbf{I}_3 and \mathbf{I}_7 where $x = 3$

$$I_j = \{n \mid j + m * 2^x\}$$

$$I_3 = \{3, 11, 19 \dots 3 + (2^\infty - 1) * 2^3\}$$

$$I_7 = \{7, 15, 23 \dots 7 + (2^\infty - 1) * 2^3\}$$

4.5. Unequally partitioned FINITE Sub-sets (F_j) of \mathbb{N}_1 .

$$(4.10) \quad F_j = \begin{cases} \{n \mid n = 1\} & \text{if } j = 0 \\ \{n \mid 2^{j-1} + 1 \leq n \leq 2^j\} & \text{if } j \geq 1 \end{cases}$$

$$(4.11) \quad |F_0| = \frac{|F_{j_1}|}{2^{j_1-1}} = \frac{|F_{j_2}|}{2^{j_2-1}} = 1 \quad (\text{for any } j_1 \geq 1 \text{ and any } j_2 \geq 1)$$

The infinite set \mathbb{N}_1 can also be unequally partitioned into infinite sub-sets $F_j \in \{F_0, F_1, F_2, \dots, F_\infty\}$. Note that $j = \lceil \log_2(\text{Any } n_O \in F_j) \rceil$.

Example 4.3. FINITE Sub-sets.

$$F_0 = \{1\}$$

$$F_1 = \{2\}$$

$$F_2 = \{3, 4\}$$

$$F_3 = \{5, 6, 7, 8\}$$

$$F_4 = \{9, 10, 11, 12, 13, 14, 15, 16\}$$

$$F_\infty = \{2^{\infty-1} + 1, 2^{\infty-1} + 2, 2^{\infty-1} + 3, \dots, 2^\infty\}$$

$$\therefore F_0 \cup F_1 \cup F_2 \cup F_3 \dots \cup F_\infty = \mathbb{N}_1$$

$$\therefore |F_0| = \frac{|F_1|}{2^0} = \frac{|F_2|}{2^1} = \frac{|F_3|}{2^2} \dots = \frac{|F_\infty|}{2^{\infty-1}} = \mathbf{1}$$

$$\therefore |F_0| + \frac{|F_1|}{2^0} + \frac{|F_2|}{2^1} + \frac{|F_3|}{2^2} \dots + \frac{|F_\infty|}{2^{\infty-1}} = |\mathbb{N}_1| = \infty$$

4.6. Relation of FINITE Sub-sets (F_j) to INFINITE Sub-sets (I_j).

Each member of F_j is a member an ∞ number of I_j since for every $x \in \mathbb{N}_0$ the union of all $I_j = \mathbb{N}_1$.

Example 4.4.

$F_3 = \{5, 6, 7, 8\} = 5^{\text{th}}, 6^{\text{th}}, 7^{\text{th}}$ and 8^{th} Members of the Set I_1 where $x = 0$

$F_3 = \{5, 6, 7, 8\} = 3^{\text{rd}}$ and 4^{th} Member of 2 Sets $I_{j=\{1,2\}}$ where $x = 1$

$F_3 = \{5, 6, 7, 8\} = 2^{\text{nd}}$ Member of 4 Sets $I_{j=\{1,2,3,4\}}$ where $x = 2$

$F_3 = \{5, 6, 7, 8\} = 1^{\text{st}}$ Member of 4 Sets of $I_{j=\{5,6,7,8\}}$ where $x = 0\{3, 4, 5, \dots, \infty\}$

4.7. Energy Value (EV).

$$(4.12) \quad EV_{\text{Step}_i} = \frac{q}{p}$$

(where $q = \text{Even Steps}$ and $p = \text{Odd Steps}$ in sequence)

The ratio of Short-cut Collatz Function *Even Steps* to *Odd Steps* in a sequence at Step_i . Until the first *Odd Step* in a sequence, $EV = \infty_{\text{undefined}}$.

4.8. Energy Level (EL).

$$(4.13) \quad EL_{\text{Step}_i} = q$$

(where $q = \text{Even Steps}$ in sequence)

The Energy Level of $f(n_O)_{\text{Step}_i}$ at Step_i . Since Energy Values, although valuable to this proof, are somewhat chaotic, Energy Levels provide a much more consistent and stable means of tracking a sequence's progress towards a solution where $f(n_O)_{\text{Step}_i} < n_O$.

As will be shown in this proof, with every additional *Even Step*, the Energy Level of $f(n_O)_{\text{Step}_i}$ will increase an additional (+1) Energy Level above Ground Energy Level, which is defined later, while any *Odd Step* keeps $f(n_O)_{\text{Step}_i}$ at the previous Energy Level.

4.9. Ground Energy Value & Level (GEV & GEL).

$$(4.14) \quad GEV = 0$$

$$(4.15) \quad GEL = EL_0$$

The GEV and GEL are the Energy Value and Level of $f(n_O)_{\text{Step}_i}$ prior to any Short-cut Collatz Function *Even Steps*. Since $EV_{\text{Step}_i} = \frac{q}{p}$, until an *Even Step* is performed, $EV_{\text{Step}_i} = 0$, since the numerator is 0.

4.10. Energy Level Value (ELV).

$$(4.16) \quad ELV_{\text{Step}_i} = \frac{q}{p} = \frac{EL}{i - EL}$$

The Energy Value for a particular Energy Level at Step_i . The range of ELV 's at each $\text{Step}_i = (0 \cdots \infty_{\text{undefined}})$.

4.11. Escape Energy Value (*EEV*).

$$(4.17) \quad EEV = \log_2(3) - 1$$

The *first time* $EV_{\text{Step}_i} > EEV$ in a Short-cut Collatz Function sequence then $f(n_O)_{\text{Step}_i} \leq n_O$. Presented as Theorem with Proof in Section 6.

4.12. Escape Energy Level (*EEL*).

$$(4.18) \quad EEL_{\text{Step}_i} = \lceil p * (\log_2(3) - 1) \rceil = TUEL_{\text{Step}_i} \quad (\text{x-axis} = \text{Odd Steps})$$

$$(4.19) \quad EEL_{\text{Step}_i} = \lceil i - i * \log_3(2) \rceil = TUEL_{\text{Step}_i} \quad (\text{x-axis} = i = \text{All Steps})$$

The lowest Energy Level at Step_{*i*} where $EV > EEV$ and provided $n_O > 4614$ then $n_i < n_O$.⁸ For all n_O , the *first time* $EL = EEL$, then $n_i < n_O$.

The $EEL = TUEL$ because Energy Level numbering begins with 0 at GEL which is EL_0 . Two equations are provided depending on whether the x -axis of plot will be *All* steps or *Odd* steps.

4.13. One Energy Value and Level (*OEV* & *OEL*).

$$(4.20) \quad OEV = \frac{\log_2(n_O)}{p} + (\log_2(3) - 1)$$

$$(4.21) \quad OEL = \lceil \log_2(n_O) + p * (\log_2(3) - 1) \rceil$$

(where if $q = OEL$ then $n_{(i=p+q)} \in F_0$)

The first time $EV_{\text{Step}_i} > OEV$ or $EL > \log_2(n_O) + p * (\log_2(3) - 1)$ in a Short-cut Collatz Function sequence then $n_i = 1$. Presented as a Theorem with Proof in Section 8.

4.14. Irregular Finite Sub-set Membership Lines ($f(F_q)$).

$$(4.22) \quad f(F_q) = \lceil \log_2(n_O) + p * (\log_2(3) - 1) \rceil - q$$

Where: $n_O \in F_j$
and: $p \in \{0, 1, 2, \dots, \text{until NEWFIRST } n_i \in F_0 = 1\}$
and: $q \in \{0 \leq q \leq j\}$

The Irregular Finite Sub-set Membership Lines from F_j to F_0 are plotted where the y -axis is the number of *Even* steps and the x -axis is the number of *Odd* steps, (Figure 3). When a sequence is plotted starting at $n_O \in F_j$ until $n_i \in F_0 = 1$ then the plots for each $n_i \in F_q$ where $q \in \{0 \leq q \leq j\}$ will fall on ONLY of the Irregular Finite Sub-set Membership Line associated with Sub-set F_q . If $n_i \in F_{q>j}$, then it will be plotted below the Irregular Finite Sub-set Membership Lines for F_j . NOTE: $f(F_j) = \lceil \log_2(n_O) + p * (\log_2(3) - 1) \rceil - j \neq EEL = \lceil p * (\log_2(3) - 1) \rceil$

⁸For $n_O \leq 4614$, there are 593 Outliers that result in $f(n)_{\text{Step}_i} > n_O$ even though $EV_{\text{Step}_i} > EEV$. As an example, this first occurs with the integer $n_O = 7$ which solves at Step₇ to 5 (< n_O) with an $EV = 0.75$ (> EEV) but at Step₈, solves to 8 (> n_O) even though the $EV = 0.6$ (> EEV). The last Outlier is $n_O = 4614$. All of the Outliers have previously solved to (< n_O) and therefore do not change the validity of the proof the first time $EV > EEV$. All of these Outliers will again solve to $n_i < n_O$ at a future Step_{*i*}. See Sub-section 10.2 for further explanation and discussion.

4.15. Total Unsolved & Solved Energy Levels (*TUEL* & *TSEL*).

$$(4.23) \quad TUEL_{\text{Step}_i} = \lceil i - i * \log_3(2) \rceil = EEL_{\text{Step}_i} \quad \text{where } i \geq 1$$

$$(4.24) \quad TSEL_{\text{Step}_i} = \lfloor 1 + i * \log_3(2) \rfloor \quad \text{where } i \geq 1$$

The Total Number of Solved and Unsolved Energy Levels at each Step $_i$, where EL_{Solved} has $EV > EEV$ and EL_{Unsolved} has $EV < EEV$.⁹

4.16. Total Available Energy Levels & Values (*TAEL* & *TAEV*).

$$(4.25) \quad TAEL_{\text{Step}_i} = TAEV_{\text{Step}_i} = i + 1 = TSEL_{\text{Step}_i} + TUEL_{\text{Step}_i}$$

The number of Possible Energy Levels and Values at Step $_i$.

Example 4.5. Step $_5$ has:

- 32 Ternary *Parity* sequences (22222, 22221, ..., 21111, 11111)
- 6 Total Available Energy Levels (0, 1, 2, 3, 4, 5)
- 6 Total Available Energy Values (0, 0.25, 0.75, 1.5, 4, $\infty_{\text{undefined}}$)
- *NRF* (defined later) (1, 5, 10, 10, 5, 1) - Pascal's Triangle Row 6 (Step $_5$)
- *UNRF* (defined later) (1, 3, 0, 0, 0, 0) - Pascal-like Triangle Row 6 (Step $_5$)

4.17. Ratio of TUEL/TSEL ($\frac{TUEL}{TSEL}$).

$$(4.26) \quad \lim_{i \rightarrow \infty} f\left(\frac{i - i * \log_3(2)}{1 + i * \log_3(2)}\right) = \log_2(3) - 1$$

$$(4.27) \quad \overline{\lim}_{i \rightarrow \infty} f\left(\frac{(\log_2(3))^2}{i} + \frac{i - i * \log_3(2)}{1 + i * \log_3(2)}\right) = \log_2(3) - 1$$

$$(4.28) \quad \frac{i - i * \log_3(2)}{1 + i * \log_3(2)} < \frac{\lceil i - i * \log_3(2) \rceil}{\lfloor 1 + i * \log_3(2) \rfloor} < \frac{(\log_2(3))^2}{i} + \frac{i - i * \log_3(2)}{1 + i * \log_3(2)}$$

Evaluating the ratio of $\frac{TUEL_{\text{Step}_i}}{TSEL_{\text{Step}_i}}$ yields the above and the curves using upper and lower limits perfectly contain the results of the erratic ceiling and floor ratio function plot. In addition, the Average Ratio Curve has a lower limit of $\log_2(3) - 1$.

$$(4.29) \quad \text{Average Ratio } \frac{TUEL_{\text{Step}_i}}{TSEL_{\text{Step}_i}} \text{ curve} = \frac{i - i * \log_3(2)}{1 + i * \log_3(2)} + \frac{(\log_2(3))^2}{2 * i}$$

$$(4.30) \quad \lim_{i \rightarrow \infty} f\left(\frac{i - i * \log_3(2)}{1 + i * \log_3(2)} + \frac{(\log_2(3))^2}{2 * i}\right) = \log_2(3) - 1$$

$$(4.31) \quad \therefore \lim_{i \rightarrow \infty} TSEL_{\text{Step}_i} = \log_3(2) * TAEL_{\text{Step}_i} \approx 63.09\% * TAEL_{\text{Step}_i}$$

$$(4.32) \quad \therefore \lim_{i \rightarrow \infty} TUEL_{\text{Step}_i} = (1 - \log_3(2)) * TAEL_{\text{Step}_i} \approx 36.91\% * TAEL_{\text{Step}_i}^{10}$$

⁹A new Unsolved Energy Level, where $EV_L < (\log_2(3) - 1)$, is added anytime there is a Step $_i$ where $i = UST$ (Unallowable Stopping Time).

¹⁰It may first appear from this limit that $\approx 36.91\%$ of $n_O \in \mathbb{N}_1$ will never solve to $n_i < n_O$. Due to the, to be proven, binomial nature of the Short-cut Collatz function, with every additional Step $_i$, the % of \mathbb{N}_1 that have never reached $n_i < n_O$ and occupy these Unsolved Energy Levels (*UEL*'s) decreases until at Step $_{456}$, $< \approx 1.39 \times 10^{-8}\%$ remain unsolved. (Figure 8)

4.18. Simplified Distributive Property of Parity_(mod 2) for Subtraction.

Lemma 4.6.

$$(a - b) \pmod{2} \equiv \left| a \pmod{2} - b \pmod{2} \right|$$

This logical and simplified property is useful in the proof. ¹¹

Trivial Proof of Lemma - 4 Cases	
Both Odd	Both Even
$(Odd - Odd) \pmod{2} \equiv$	$(Even - Even) \pmod{2} \equiv$
$\left Odd \pmod{2} - Odd \pmod{2} \right $	$\left Even \pmod{2} - Even \pmod{2} \right $
$Even \pmod{2} \equiv 1 - 1 $	$Even \pmod{2} \equiv 0 - 0 $
$0 \equiv 0$	$0 \equiv 0$
Even and Odd	Odd and Even
$(Even - Odd) \pmod{2} \equiv$	$(Odd - Even) \pmod{2} \equiv$
$\left Even \pmod{2} - Odd \pmod{2} \right $	$\left Odd \pmod{2} - Even \pmod{2} \right $
$Odd \pmod{2} \equiv 0 - 1 $	$Odd \pmod{2} \equiv 1 - 0 $
$1 \equiv 1$	$1 \equiv 1$
Therefore the Lemma is True.	

4.19. Pascal and Pascal-Like Reduced Fractional Numerators.

4.19.1. *Pascal* (All I_j) - *Reduced Fractional Numerator* ($N_{L_{Step_i}}$).

$$(4.33) \quad \frac{N_{L_{Step_i}}}{GCD(2^i)} = \frac{N_{L_{Step_{(i-1)}}} + N_{(L-1)_{Step_{(i-1)}}}}{2^{(i-1)} * 2^1}$$

$$(4.34) \quad \frac{N_{L_{Step_i}}}{GCD(2^i)} = \frac{T_{L_{Step_i}}}{2^{x+z}} \text{ (Unreduced - where } z \in \mathbb{N}_0 \text{ for Finite Analysis)}$$

$$(4.35) \quad \frac{N_{L_{Step_i}}}{GCD(2^i)} = \frac{\left| A_{L_{Step_i}} \right|}{2^\infty} \text{ (Unreduced - where } z = \infty \text{ for Infinite Equation)}$$

where :

L = Number of EL_L at Step _{i}

$T_{L_{Step_i}}$ = Total Sequences ending at EL_L after Step _{i}

$A_{L_{Step_i}}$ = ALL Sub-sets I_j where $x = i$ that end at EL_L after Step _{i}

The numerator of the reduced fractional % of total distribution results generated by the infinite sub-sets, $I_j \in \{I_1, I_2, I_3, \dots, I_{2^x}\}$, where $x \in \mathbb{N}_0$ and where $m \in \{0, 1, 2, \dots, 2^z - 1\}$ and $z \in \mathbb{N}_0$, that end at a particular Energy Level at Step _{i} when the sequences are not stopped neither when $n_i < n_O$ nor when $n_i = 1$.

Provided the sample size is 2^{x+z} sequential integers, the numerators form a perfect Pascal's Triangle up to Step _{$x+z$} (Table 1). Every possible Parity Sequence at Step _{i} will be followed at least once for a total of 2^i sequences. This will be fully

¹¹Only for (mod 2), where $a < b$, the above equation simplified from $[(a - b) \pmod{2} \equiv (a \pmod{2} - b \pmod{2}) \pmod{2}]$, is also valid but, for this proof, all equations are arranged, where necessary, so that $a > b$, eliminating any possibly awkward $-Integer \pmod{2}$ confusion.

proven in the Identical and Alternating Equivalence Parity Theorem with Proof in Section 5.

Where, for each Step_{*i*}, where $m \in \{0, 1, 2, \dots, 2^{z-i} - 1\}$, the 1 on left (EL_0) and right (EL_i) sides of the triangle are generated by the sequences of the subsets:

$$I_{(j=2^i-1)} \in \{n \mid (2^i - 1) + m * 2^i\} \text{ (LEFT) and } I_{(j=2^i)} \in \{n \mid 2^i + m * 2^i\} \text{ (RIGHT)}$$

Also, analysis of a single infinite sub-set I_j , where $x \in \mathbb{N}_0$ and with a sample size is 2^z sequential integers, where:

$$j \geq 1, I_j = \{j + 0 * 2^x, j + 1 * 2^x, j + 2 * 2^x, \dots, j + (2^z - 1) * 2^x\}$$

will produce the same numerator of the reduced fractional % of total distribution results starting at Step_{*x*} up to Step_{*x+z*}. Before Step_{*x*}, all members of the sub-set follow the same parity sequence, resulting in a single numerator $N_{L\text{Step}_i} = 1$ at various Energy Levels at each Step_{*i*} depending on the actual Parity Sequence for this sub-set I_j .

4.19.2. **Pascal-Like (Unsolved I_j) Reduced Fractional Numerator ($UN_{L\text{Step}_i}$).**

$$(4.36) \quad f\left(\frac{UN_{L\text{Step}_i}}{\text{GCD}(2^i)}\right) = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{if } L \geq EEL_{\text{Step}_i} \\ \frac{UN_{L\text{Step}_{(i-1)}} + UN_{(L-1)\text{Step}_{(i-1)}}}{2^{(i-1)} * 2^1} & \text{if } L < EEL_{\text{Step}_i} \end{cases}$$

$$(4.37) \quad \frac{UN_{L\text{Step}_i}}{\text{GCD}(2^i)} = \frac{TUS_{L\text{Step}_i}}{2^{x+z}} \text{ (Unreduced - where } z \in \mathbb{N}_0 \text{ for Finite Analysis)}$$

$$(4.38) \quad \frac{UN_{L\text{Step}_i}}{\text{GCD}(2^i)} = \frac{|S_{L\text{Step}_i}|}{2^\infty} \text{ (Unreduced - where } z = \infty \text{ for Infinite Equation)}$$

where :

L = Number of EL_L at Step_{*i*}

$TUS_{L\text{Step}_i}$ = Total UNSOLVED Sequences ending at EL_L after Step_{*i*}

$S_{\text{Step}_{(i)}}$ = Set of all Surviving Subsets of I_j where $x = i$ after Step_{*i*}

$S_{L\text{Step}_{(i)}}$ = Subsets of $S_{\text{Step}_{(i)}}$ that end at EL_L after Step_{*i*}

The numerator of the reduced fractional % of UNSOLVED distribution results generated by the infinite sub-sets, $I_j \in \{I_1, I_2, I_3, \dots, I_{2^x}\}$, where $x \in \mathbb{N}_0$ and where $m \in \{0, 1, 2, \dots, 2^z - 1\}$ and $z \in \mathbb{N}_0$, that end at a particular Energy Level at Step_{*i*} when the sequences are stopped and not counted neither when $n_i < n_O$ nor when $n_i = 1$.

Provided the Sample Size is 2^{x+z} sequential integers, the numerators form Pascal-Like results up to Step_{*x+z*} (Table 3). Every possible Unsolved Parity Sequence at Step_{*i*}, where the $EV_{\text{Step}_i} < EEV$ at this Step_{*i*} and all previous Steps, will be followed at least once. This will be fully proven by combination of the Energy Value $> (\log_2(3) - 1)$ Theorem in Section 6 and the Identical and Alternating Equivalence Parity Theorem in Section 5.

4.19.3. Examples of $N_{L_{Step_i}}$ and $UN_{L_{Step_i}}$ using two different methods.**Example 4.7.** Example of $N_{L_{Step_i}}$ Table 6: Limited (Non-Infinite) Example of $N_{L_{Step_i}}$

Given:

$$I_j \in \{I_1, I_2, I_3, \dots, I_{2^x}\} \text{ where } x \in \mathbb{N}_0$$

$$I_j = \{n \mid j + m * 2^x, \text{ where } m \in \mathbb{N}_0$$

$$\text{limiting } m \in \{0, 1, 2, \dots, 2^z - 1\}, x = 2 \text{ and } z = 2\}$$

After Step₁ ($i = 1$) ($i \leq x + z \therefore NRF = \text{Pascal Numbers}$)					
Sub-sets (I_j)		Parity Sequences		Energy Levels	
$I_1 = \{1, 5, 9, 13\}$		$I_1 = \{2, 2, 2, 2\}$		$I_1 = \{0, 0, 0, 0\}$	
$I_2 = \{2, 6, 10, 14\}$		$I_2 = \{1, 1, 1, 1\}$		$I_2 = \{1, 1, 1, 1\}$	
$I_3 = \{3, 7, 11, 15\}$		$I_3 = \{2, 2, 2, 2\}$		$I_3 = \{0, 0, 0, 0\}$	
$I_4 = \{4, 8, 12, 16\}$		$I_4 = \{1, 1, 1, 1\}$		$I_4 = \{1, 1, 1, 1\}$	
UN-Reduced Fractional Distributions (After Step₁)					
EL_0	EL_1	EL_2	EL_3	EL_4	EL_5
$\frac{8}{16}$	$\frac{8}{16}$	$\frac{0}{16}$	$\frac{0}{16}$	$\frac{0}{16}$	$\frac{0}{16}$
Reduced to GCD Fractional Distributions (After Step₁)					
EL_0	EL_1	EL_2	EL_3	EL_4	EL_5
$\frac{1}{2}$	$\frac{1}{2}$	$\frac{0}{2}$	$\frac{0}{2}$	$\frac{0}{2}$	$\frac{0}{2}$
After Step₁, Numerators are 2^{nd} row ($i + 1$) of Pascals Triangle.					
Denominator is 2^i					
50% Even and 50% Odd Parity at Step _{$i-1$}					
After Step₂ ($i = 2$) ($i \leq x + z \therefore NRF = \text{Pascal Numbers}$)					
Sub-sets (I_j)		Parity Sequences		Energy Levels	
$I_1 = \{1, 5, 9, 13\}$		$I_1 = \{21, 21, 21, 21\}$		$I_1 = \{1, 1, 1, 1\}$	
$I_2 = \{2, 6, 10, 14\}$		$I_2 = \{12, 12, 12, 12\}$		$I_2 = \{1, 1, 1, 1\}$	
$I_3 = \{3, 7, 11, 15\}$		$I_3 = \{22, 22, 22, 22\}$		$I_3 = \{0, 0, 0, 0\}$	
$I_4 = \{4, 8, 12, 16\}$		$I_4 = \{11, 11, 11, 11\}$		$I_4 = \{2, 2, 2, 2\}$	
UN-Reduced Fractional Distributions (After Step₂)					
EL_0	EL_1	EL_2	EL_3	EL_4	EL_5
$\frac{4}{16}$	$\frac{8}{16}$	$\frac{4}{16}$	$\frac{0}{16}$	$\frac{0}{16}$	$\frac{0}{16}$
Reduced to GCD Fractional Distributions (After Step₂)					
EL_0	EL_1	EL_2	EL_3	EL_4	EL_5
$\frac{1}{4}$	$\frac{2}{4}$	$\frac{1}{4}$	$\frac{0}{4}$	$\frac{0}{4}$	$\frac{0}{4}$
After Step₂, Numerators are 3^{rd} row ($i + 1$) of Pascals Triangle.					
Denominator is 2^i					
50% Even and 50% Odd Parity at Step _{$i-1$}					
After Step₃ ($i = 3$) ($i \leq x + z \therefore NRF = \text{Pascal Numbers}$)					
Sub-sets (I_j)		Parity Sequences		Energy Levels	
$I_1 = \{1, 5, 9, 13\}$		$I_1 = \{212, 211, 212, 211\}$		$I_1 = \{1, 2, 1, 2\}$	
$I_2 = \{2, 6, 10, 14\}$		$I_2 = \{121, 122, 121, 122\}$		$I_2 = \{2, 1, 2, 1\}$	
$I_3 = \{3, 7, 11, 15\}$		$I_3 = \{221, 222, 221, 222\}$		$I_3 = \{1, 0, 1, 0\}$	
$I_4 = \{4, 8, 12, 16\}$		$I_4 = \{112, 111, 112, 111\}$		$I_4 = \{2, 3, 2, 3\}$	
UN-Reduced Fractional Distributions (After Step₃)					
EL_0	EL_1	EL_2	EL_3	EL_4	EL_5
$\frac{2}{16}$	$\frac{6}{16}$	$\frac{6}{16}$	$\frac{2}{16}$	$\frac{0}{16}$	$\frac{0}{16}$

Continued on next page

Table 6 – continued from previous page

LIMITED EXAMPLE OF $N_{L\text{Step}_i}$					
Reduced to GCD Fractional Distributions (After Step ₃)					
EL_0 $\frac{1}{8}$	EL_1 $\frac{3}{8}$	EL_2 $\frac{3}{8}$	EL_3 $\frac{1}{8}$	EL_4 $\frac{0}{8}$	EL_5 $\frac{0}{8}$
After Step₃, Numerators are 4th row ($i + 1$) of Pascals Triangle. Denominator is 2^i 50% <i>Even</i> and 50% <i>Odd</i> Parity at Step _{$i-1$}					
After Step₄ ($i = 4$) ($i < x + z \therefore NRF = \text{Pascal Numbers}$)					
Sub-sets (I_j)		Parity Sequences		Energy Levels	
$I_1 = \{1, 5, 9, 13\}$		$I_1 = \{2121, 2111, 2122, 2112\}$		$I_1 = \{2, 3, 1, 2\}$	
$I_2 = \{2, 6, 10, 14\}$		$I_2 = \{1212, 1221, 1211, 1222\}$		$I_2 = \{2, 2, 3, 1\}$	
$I_3 = \{3, 7, 11, 15\}$		$I_3 = \{2211, 2221, 2212, 2222\}$		$I_3 = \{2, 1, 1, 0\}$	
$I_4 = \{4, 8, 12, 16\}$		$I_4 = \{1121, 1112, 1122, 1111\}$		$I_4 = \{3, 3, 2, 4\}$	
<i>Already</i>					
Reduced to GCD Fractional Distributions (After Step ₄)					
EL_0 $\frac{1}{16}$	EL_1 $\frac{4}{16}$	EL_2 $\frac{6}{16}$	EL_3 $\frac{4}{16}$	EL_4 $\frac{1}{16}$	EL_5 $\frac{0}{16}$
After Step₄, Numerators are 5th row ($i + 1$) of Pascals Triangle. Denominator is 2^i 50% <i>Even</i> and 50% <i>Odd</i> Parity at Step _{$i-1$}					
After Step₅ ($i = 5$) ($i > x + z \therefore NRF \neq \text{Pascal Numbers}$)					
Sub-sets (I_j)		Parity Sequences		Energy Levels	
$I_1 = \{1, 5, 9, 13\}$		$I_1 = \{21212, 21112, 21222, 21121\}$		$I_1 = \{2, 3, 1, 3\}$	
$I_2 = \{2, 6, 10, 14\}$		$I_2 = \{12121, 12211, 12111, 12221\}$		$I_2 = \{3, 3, 4, 2\}$	
$I_3 = \{3, 7, 11, 15\}$		$I_3 = \{22111, 22212, 22121, 22221\}$		$I_3 = \{3, 1, 2, 1\}$	
$I_4 = \{4, 8, 12, 16\}$		$I_4 = \{11212, 11121, 11221, 11112\}$		$I_4 = \{3, 4, 3, 4\}$	
<i>Already</i>					
Reduced to GCD Fractional Distributions (After Step ₅)					
EL_0 $\frac{0}{16}$	EL_1 $\frac{3}{16}$	EL_2 $\frac{3}{16}$	EL_3 $\frac{7}{16}$	EL_4 $\frac{3}{16}$	EL_5 $\frac{0}{16}$
After Step₅, Numerators are <i>NOT</i> 6th row ($i + 1$) of Pascals Triangle. Denominator is 2^{i-1} <i>NOT</i> 2^i <u>NOT</u> 50% <i>Even</i> and 50% <i>Odd</i> Parity at Step_{$i-1$} 62.5% <i>Even</i> and 37.5% <i>Odd</i> Parity at Step _{$i-1$}					
Note that Setting $x = 2$ and $z = 3 \therefore x + z = 5$ where $m \in \{0, 1, 2, \dots, 2^z - 1\}$ would have resulted a sample size of 32 sequential integers, whose Numerators after Step ₅ would have been the 6 th row ($i + 1$) of Pascals Triangle and would have resulted in 50% <i>Even</i> and 50% <i>Odd</i> Parity at Step _{$i-1$}					
Example Complete					

Example 4.8. Example of $UN_{L_{\text{Step}_i}}$

Table 7: Limited (Infinite) Example of $UN_{L_{\text{Step}_i}}$

Given:

$$I_j \in \{I_1, I_2, I_3, \dots, I_{2^x}\}$$

$$I_j = \{n \mid j + m * 2^x, \text{ where } m \in \mathbb{N}_0, x = i,$$

$$\text{non-limiting } m \in \{0, 1, 2, \dots, 2^z - 1\}, x \in \mathbb{N}_0 \text{ and } z = \infty\}$$

After Step₁ ($x = i = 1$)						$EEL = 1$
Sub-sets (I_j)		Parity Sequences		Energy Levels		
$I_1 = \{1, 3, 5, \dots$ $, (1 + (2^\infty - 1)) * 2^1\}$		$I_1 = \{2, \dots\}$		$I_1 = \{0, \dots\} < EEL$		
$I_2 = \{2, 4, 6, \dots$ $, (2 + (2^\infty - 1)) * 2^1\}$		$I_2 = \{1, \dots\}$		$I_2 = \{1, \dots\} = EEL$		
Reduced to GCD Surviving Fractional Distributions (After Step₁)						
EL_0	EL_1	EL_2	EL_3	EL_4	Solved	
$\frac{1}{2}$	$\frac{0}{2}$	$\frac{0}{2}$	$\frac{0}{2}$	$\frac{0}{2}$	$\frac{1}{2}$	
After Step₂ ($x = i = 2$)						$EEL = 1$
Surviving Sub-sets (I_j)		Parity Sequences		Energy Levels		
$I_1 = \{1, 5, 9, \dots$ $, (1 + (2^\infty - 1)) * 2^2\}$		$I_1 = \{21, \dots\}$		$I_1 = \{1, \dots\} = EEL$		
$I_3 = \{3, 7, 11, \dots$ $, (3 + (2^\infty - 1)) * 2^2\}$		$I_3 = \{22, \dots\}$		$I_3 = \{0, \dots\} < EEL$		
Reduced to GCD Fractional Distributions (After Step₂)						
EL_0	EL_1	EL_2	EL_3	EL_4	Solved	
$\frac{1}{4}$	$\frac{0}{4}$	$\frac{0}{4}$	$\frac{0}{4}$	$\frac{0}{4}$	$\frac{3}{4}$	
After Step₃ ($x = i = 3$)						$EEL = 2$
Surviving Sub-sets (I_j)		Parity Sequences		Energy Levels		
$I_3 = \{3, 11, 19, \dots$ $, (3 + (2^\infty - 1)) * 2^3\}$		$I_3 = \{221, \dots\}$		$I_3 = \{1, \dots\} < EEL$		
$I_7 = \{7, 15, 23, \dots$ $, (7 + (2^\infty - 1)) * 2^3\}$		$I_7 = \{222, \dots\}$		$I_7 = \{0, \dots\} < EEL$		
Reduced to GCD Fractional Distributions (After Step₃)						
EL_0	EL_1	EL_2	EL_3	EL_4	Solved	
$\frac{1}{8}$	$\frac{1}{8}$	$\frac{0}{8}$	$\frac{0}{8}$	$\frac{0}{8}$	$\frac{6}{8}$	
After Step₄ ($x = i = 4$)						$EEL = 2$
Surviving Sub-sets (I_j)		Parity Sequences		Energy Levels		
$I_3 = \{3, 19, 25, \dots$ $, (3 + (2^\infty - 1)) * 2^4\}$		$I_3 = \{2211, \dots\}$		$I_3 = \{2, \dots\} = EEL$		
$I_{11} = \{11, 27, 43, \dots$ $, (11 + (2^\infty - 1)) * 2^4\}$		$I_{11} = \{2212, \dots\}$		$I_{11} = \{1, \dots\} < EEL$		
$I_7 = \{7, 23, 39, \dots$ $, (7 + (2^\infty - 1)) * 2^4\}$		$I_7 = \{2221, \dots\}$		$I_7 = \{1, \dots\} < EEL$		
$I_{15} = \{15, 31, 47, \dots$ $, (15 + (2^\infty - 1)) * 2^4\}$		$I_{15} = \{2222, \dots\}$		$I_{15} = \{0, \dots\} < EEL$		
Reduced to GCD Fractional Distributions (After Step₄)						
EL_0	EL_1	EL_2	EL_3	EL_4	Solved	
$\frac{1}{16}$	$\frac{2}{16}$	$\frac{0}{16}$	$\frac{0}{16}$	$\frac{0}{16}$	$\frac{13}{16}$	

Continued on next page

Table 7 – continued from previous page

LIMITED EXAMPLE OF $UN_{L_{Step_i}}$					
After Step₅ ($x = i = 5$)			$EEL = 2$		
Surviving Sub-sets (I_j)	Parity Sequences	Energy Levels			
$I_{11} = \{11, 43, 75, \dots$ $, (11 + (2^\infty - 1)) * 2^5\}$	$I_{11} = \{22121, \dots\}$	$I_{11} = \{2, \dots\} = EEL$			
$I_{27} = \{27, 59, 91, \dots$ $, (27 + (2^\infty - 1)) * 2^5\}$	$I_{27} = \{22122, \dots\}$	$I_{27} = \{1, \dots\} < EEL$			
$I_7 = \{7, 39, 71, \dots$ $, (7 + (2^\infty - 1)) * 2^5\}$	$I_7 = \{22212, \dots\}$	$I_7 = \{1, \dots\} < EEL$			
$I_{23} = \{23, 55, 87, \dots$ $, (23 + (2^\infty - 1)) * 2^5\}$	$I_{23} = \{22211, \dots\}$	$I_{23} = \{2, \dots\} = EEL$			
$I_{15} = \{15, 47, 79, \dots$ $, (15 + (2^\infty - 1)) * 2^5\}$	$I_{15} = \{22221, \dots\}$	$I_{15} = \{1, \dots\} < EEL$			
$I_{31} = \{31, 63, 95, \dots$ $, (31 + (2^\infty - 1)) * 2^5\}$	$I_{31} = \{22222, \dots\}$	$I_{31} = \{0, \dots\} < EEL$			
Reduced to GCD Fractional Distributions (After Step₅)					
EL_0	EL_1	EL_2	EL_3	EL_4	Solved
$\frac{1}{32}$	$\frac{3}{32}$	$\frac{0}{32}$	$\frac{0}{32}$	$\frac{0}{32}$	$\frac{28}{32}$
After Step₆ ($x = i = 6$)			$EEL = 3$		
Surviving Sub-sets (I_j)	Parity Sequences	Energy Levels			
$I_{27} = \{27, 91, 151, \dots\}$	$I_{27} = \{221222, \dots\}$	$I_{27} = \{1, \dots\} < EEL$			
$I_{59} = \{59, 123, 187, \dots\}$	$I_{59} = \{221221, \dots\}$	$I_{59} = \{2, \dots\} < EEL$			
$I_7 = \{7, 71, 135, \dots\}$	$I_7 = \{222121, \dots\}$	$I_7 = \{2, \dots\} < EEL$			
$I_{39} = \{39, 103, 167, \dots\}$	$I_{39} = \{222122, \dots\}$	$I_{39} = \{1, \dots\} < EEL$			
$I_{15} = \{15, 79, 143, \dots\}$	$I_{15} = \{222211, \dots\}$	$I_{15} = \{2, \dots\} < EEL$			
$I_{47} = \{47, 111, 175, \dots\}$	$I_{47} = \{222212, \dots\}$	$I_{47} = \{1, \dots\} < EEL$			
$I_{31} = \{31, 95, 159, \dots\}$	$I_{31} = \{222221, \dots\}$	$I_{31} = \{1, \dots\} < EEL$			
$I_{63} = \{63, 127, 191, \dots\}$	$I_{63} = \{222222, \dots\}$	$I_{63} = \{0, \dots\} < EEL$			
Reduced to GCD Fractional Distributions (After Step₆)					
EL_0	EL_1	EL_2	EL_3	EL_4	Solved
$\frac{1}{64}$	$\frac{4}{64}$	$\frac{3}{64}$	$\frac{0}{64}$	$\frac{0}{64}$	$\frac{56}{64}$
After Step₇ ($x = i = 7$)			$EEL = 3$		
Surviving Sub-sets (I_{j_s})	Last Parity's	Energy Levels			
$I_{j_s} = \{I_{27}, I_{91}, I_{123},$ $I_{59}, I_{71}, I_{39}, I_{103},$ $I_{15}, I_{79}, I_{47}, I_{111},$ $I_{31}, I_{95}, I_{63}, I_{127}\}$	$I_{j_s} = \{2, 1, 1, 2$ $1, 2, 1, 2$ $1, 2, 1, 2$ $2, 1, 1, 2\}$	$I_{j_s} = \{1, 2, 2$ $2, 2, 1$ $2, 2, 1$ $1, 2, 1, 0\}$			
Reduced to GCD Fractional Distributions (After Step₇)					
EL_0	EL_1	EL_2	EL_3	EL_4	Solved
$\frac{1}{128}$	$\frac{5}{128}$	$\frac{7}{128}$	$\frac{0}{128}$	$\frac{0}{128}$	$\frac{115}{128}$
After each Step_i, Surviving Numerators are the ($i + 1$) row of the Pascal-like Triangle and the Denominator is 2^i 50% Even and 50% Odd Parity at Step_{$i-1$} After each Step, split ALL surviving I_j, where $x = i$, into I_j and I_{j+2^i}, where $x = i + 1$					
Example Complete					

4.20. Weighted Arithmetic Mean Unsolved Energy Values (\overline{UEV}_{W_i}).

$$(4.39) \quad \overline{UEV}_{W_i} = \frac{(UEV_{0_i} + UEV_{1_i} + UEV_{2_i} + \cdots + UEV_{(EEL-1)_i})}{(UN_{0_i} + UN_{1_i} + UN_{2_i} + \cdots + UN_{(EEL-1)_i})}$$

where: $UEV_{L_i} \equiv UEV_{L_{Step_i}}$ and $UN_{L_i} \equiv UN_{L_{Step_i}}$ (To shorten expressions)

$$UEV_{L_i} = UN_{L_i} * ELV_{L_{Step_i}} = UN_{L_i} * \frac{L}{i-L}$$

$L =$ Number of EL_L at Step $_i$

When analyzing $f(n_O)$ where: $n_O = (1, 2, 3, \dots, 2^{(x+z)})^{12}$, up to and including Step $_{(x+z)}$, the distribution of results that end on different Energy Levels at each Step $_i$ is not even. An Arithmetic Mean of Unsolved Energy Values is of no value. It is necessary to calculate a Weighted Arithmetic Mean for Unsolved Energy Values (\overline{UEV}_{W_i}) at each Step $_i$ by multiplying the number of Unsolved results at a particular Energy Level at each Step $_i$ ($UN_{L_{Step_i}}$) by the Energy Level Value of that Energy Level at that Step $_i$ ($ELV_{L_{Step_i}}$) for all Energy Levels where $EL < EEL$. Then these results are summed and divided by the total number of results where where $EL < EEL$. The result is a Weighted Arithmetic Mean for Unsolved Energy Values at Step $_i$.

With each additional iteration, i , as $i \rightarrow \infty$, \overline{UEV}_{W_i} approaches closer and closer to $\log_2(3) - 1$ but will never reach it, since infinity is forever. This strongly suggests that, where $n_O = (1, 2, 3, \dots, 2^{x \leq \infty})$, inevitably, $n_i < n_O$.

Calculations of \overline{UEV}_{W_i} and the Unsolved/Solved Sub-set percentages for each Step $_i$, where $i \in \{1, 2, 3, \dots, 456\}$ show that for all Sub-sets $I_j \in \{I_1, I_2, I_3, \dots, I_{2^x}\}$, where $x = 456$, that $> \approx 99.9999999861\%$ of the Sub-sets have solved to $< n_O$ by Step $_{456}$, while $< \approx 1.39 \times 10^{-8}\%$ remain unsolved. These percentages would only improve with each further iteration. (Figure 8)

4.21. Folded Cumulative Probability Distribution Curves. A method is presented of plotting Cumulative Probability Curves by creating a 2D (top-down) look at a 3D symmetric matrix where the y -axis is the number of *Even* steps, the x -axis is the number of *Odd* steps and the z -axis = The Partial Diagonal Sum Percentages of the Pascal Matrix Value $_{(at\ xy)}$. In addition, each Diagonal $_i =$ Step $_i$. (Figure 10)

The Partial Diagonal Sum Percentage Matrix Value $_{(at\ xy)}$, at each (Diagonal $_i$), is found which is greater than or equal to the percentage for the curve being generated. The Cumulative Probability Curve, for that percentage, is then plotted at $y = -1$ and $x = +1$ to generate a conservative curve¹³ which will follow, approximately and slightly below, the contour of the associated value of z for the percentage curve being generated. See example for 10% Probability in Table 4 and Figure 9.

There are three (3) straight line Distribution Curve solutions. These are the 50% Distribution Line (with a slope of 1 and y-intercept of 0) and the two Distribution Curves at the extremes of x-axis and y-axis. All other solutions are curves whose slope will approach but never reach 1. Above the 50% Distribution Line, the slope will start greater than 1 and then decrease toward, but never reach 1. Below the

¹²Or all Sub-sets $I_j \in \{I_1, I_2, I_3, \dots, I_{2^{x+z}}\}$.

¹³Cumulative Probability Curves above the 50% line would instead be plotted at $y = +1$ and $x = -1$ to generate a Conservative Curve.

50% Distribution Line, the slope will start less than 1 and then increase toward,, but never reach 1.

When the Proof Lines for $n_i < n_O$ and $n_i = 1$ are also plotted with this curve, it is clear that there is an always will be a point of intersection, no matter how low an Probability Distribution % is calculated. ¹⁴

4.22. Cumulative Exactability Curves. The same method used to plot Cumulative Probability Curves is also used to plot what will be referred to as “Cumulative Exactability Curves”. (Figure 11)

The curves are generated by summing the pascal-like matrix values (z) for each element (Energy Level) for that *diagonal* row (Full Step) starting at the bottom until the total is greater than or equal to the fractional percent for the curve being generated. The Cumulative Exactability Curve, for that percentage, is then plotted at $q = y = \text{Total Energy Levels Summed} - 1$ and $p = x = \text{Odd Steps} = \text{Full Step} - \text{Total Energy Levels Summed} + 1$.

Since the function stops when $EV > EEV$, there are no “Folded” curves above the 50% Probability Distribution line and only one(1) *possible* straight line Distribution Curve solution along the x -axis at GEL . All other solutions are curves whose slope will start less than 1 and then increase toward 1 but never reach 1.

When the Proof Line for $n_i < n_O$ is also plotted with this curve, it is clear that there is an always will be a point of intersection, no matter how low an Exactability Distribution % is calculated. ¹⁴

It is important to note that the slope of any Cumulative Exactability Curve increases more rapidly and always intersects the $n_i < n_O$ limit at an earlier Step than the Cumulative Probability Curve of the equivalent approximate percentage. See examples for 10% in Tables 4, 5 and for $\frac{1}{2^{26}}$ % and $\frac{1}{2^{31.5}}$ % in Figure 12.

4.23. Energy Level Curves and Increase Lines. These curves and lines are only applicable in the first plot where y -axis = EV and x -axis = *All* steps and represent all the possible paths that a sequence can take. Each Energy Level Curve will have one point of intersection with each Energy Level Increase Line, and vice versa. They are not needed in the plot where y -axis = *Even* steps and x -axis = *Odd* steps, since these sequence paths are converted to straight horizontal and vertical lines.

4.23.1. *Energy Level Curves (ELC).*

$$(4.40) \quad ELC_{L_{\text{Step}_i}} = \frac{i}{i-L} - 1 \text{ where } i = (L, L+1, L+2, \dots, \infty)$$

$$\lim_{i \rightarrow \infty} f\left(\frac{i}{i-L} - 1\right) = 0$$

where: $L = \text{Number of } EL_L \text{ at Step}_i$

Iterative Curves, representing the path taken by *Odd* steps, and also representing the Energy Level Value (ELV) of each Energy Level at each Step $_i$.

¹⁴The only Distribution Curves that would never intersect a Proof Line would be an Probability or Exactability % = 0 which would be a straight line along the x -axis. As will be shown in the proof, the only integers that could *possibly* meet this requirement, would be members of the Sub-set, where $x = \infty$, where $I_{(2^\infty-1)} = \{n \mid n = 2^\infty - 1 + m * 2^\infty \text{ where } m \in \mathbb{N}_0\}$, but, as will be shown in the proof, 50% of this Sub-set will have the Alternate Parity Sequence at Step $_{\infty+1}$, which leads to a logical reductio ad absurdum proof.

The value of $ELC_{0_{Step_i}} = 0$ for all iterations (straight vertical line). For all other curves, at first iteration where $i = L$, $ELC_{L_{Step_L}} = \infty - 1 \equiv \infty$. As L increases, the slope, where the curve intersects the EEV line increases (becomes less negative).

4.23.2. *Energy Level Increase Lines(ELI).*

$$(4.41) \quad EIL_{L_{Step_i}} = \frac{i}{L} - 1 \text{ where } i = (L, L + 1, L + 2, \dots, \infty)$$

$$\lim_{i \rightarrow \infty} f\left(\frac{i}{L} - 1\right) = \infty$$

where: $L =$ Number of EL_L at Step $_i$

Iterative Lines, representing the path taken by *Even* steps, that also represent the Energy Level Value (ELV) after each Energy Level Change at each Step $_i$.

All Energy Level Increase Lines radiate from the y -intercept $= -1$ with an ever decreasing slope that never becomes *Negative*. Slope $= \frac{1}{L}$.

4.24. **Value of n_{Step_i} of $f(n_{Original})$ (n_{Step_i}).**

$$(4.42) \quad f^i(n_{Original}) = n_{Step_i} = n_{Original} + w = \frac{3^p * n_{Original}}{2^i} + \frac{b}{2^i}$$

At Step $_i$ of $f(n_{Original})$, $n_{Original}$ will have undergone a change in integer value, resulting in an integer, n_{Step_i} , that is either larger than or smaller than the original integer, $n_{Original}$. The new integer value, n_{Step_i} , can be represented as:

$$(4.43) \quad f^i(n_{Original}) = n_{Step_i} = n_{Original} + w$$

where: $w =$ Integer to add to $n_{Original}$ to make equivalence where $w \in \mathbb{Z}$

If $w = 0$ then $n_{Step_i} = n_{Original}$ (Any Terminal Loop)

If $w < 0$ then $n_{Step_i} < n_{Original}$

If $w > 0$ then $n_{Step_i} > n_{Original}$

The new integer value, n_{Step_i} , can also be represented using the equation below, derived from the New (Ternary) *Parity* Short-cut Collatz Function Equation 4.4:

$$(4.44) \quad f^i(n_{Original}) = n_{Step_i} = \frac{3^p * n_{Original} + b}{2^i} = \frac{3^p * n_{Original}}{2^i} + \frac{b}{2^i}$$

where:

- (1) $p =$ Number of *Odd* Parity Steps in the Parity Sequence to Step $_i$
 - Since 3^p is a power of 3, $3^p \pmod{2} \equiv 1$ and it will always be *Odd*
- (2) $b =$ Variable to hold, and keep separate, the numerator of the right hand fraction (“+1 side”) of the sum of the New (Binary) *Parity* Short-cut Collatz Function. As will be shown in proof, the exact value of b is not critical to the proof, only the limits and parity.
 - Value of b

$$(4.45) \quad f(b_{Step_i}) = \begin{cases} 3 * b_{Step_{(i-1)}} + 2^{(i-1)} & \text{if } n_{Step_{(i-1)}} \pmod{2} \equiv 1 \\ b_{Step_{(i-1)}} & \text{if } n_{Step_{(i-1)}} \pmod{2} \equiv 0 \end{cases}$$

- Limits of b

$$0 \leq b \leq 3^i - 2^i$$

- Minimum Value of b_{Step_i} for continuous *Even* Parity Steps

$$b_{\text{Step}_i} = 0$$

- Maximum Value of b_{Step_i} for continuous *Odd* Parity Steps

$$b_{\text{Step}_i} = 3^i - 2^i$$

Trivial proof since for continuous *Odd* Parity Steps:

$$f(b_{\text{Step}_i}) = \begin{cases} 3 * b_{\text{Step}_{(i-1)}} + 2^{(i-1)} & \text{if } n_{\text{Step}_{(i-1)}} \pmod{2} \equiv 1 \end{cases}$$

Comparing recursive results at Step_{*i*} for $b_{\text{Step}_i} = 3 * b_{\text{Step}_{(i-1)}} + 2^{(i-1)}$ and explicit results Step_{*i*} for $b_{\text{Step}_i} = 3^i - 2^i$ quickly proves that:

$$3^i - 2^i = 3 * b_{\text{Step}_{(i-1)}} + 2^{(i-1)}$$

$$\therefore \text{For any Step}_i \quad 0 \leq b \leq 3^i - 2^i$$

- Parity of b

$$n_{\text{Original}} \pmod{2} \equiv b \pmod{2}$$

- If n_{Original} is *Odd*, the first Step is a *Odd* Parity Step, therefore $b = 2^{(1-1)} = 1$ which is *Odd*. All subsequent *Odd* Parity Steps will add a $2^{(i-1)}$ which will be *Even* and b will be *Odd*.
- If n_{Original} is *Even*, the first Step is a *Even* Parity Step so the *Odd* value 1 will not be added. All subsequent *Odd* Parity Steps will add a $2^{(i-1)}$ value which will be *Even* and b will be *Even*.

- Limits of $\frac{b}{2^{i * \log_2(3)}}$:

$$0 \leq \frac{b}{2^{i * \log_2(3)}} < 1$$

- Lower Limit proof is trivial using lower limit of $0 \leq b$

$$\therefore 0 \leq \frac{b}{2^{i * \log_2(3)}}$$

- Upper Limit proof is also trivial using upper limit of $b \leq 3^i - 2^i$

$$\frac{b}{2^{i * \log_2(3)}} = \frac{b}{3^i} = \frac{3^i - 2^i}{3^i} = 1 - \frac{2^i}{3^i} < 1$$

- The form $\frac{b}{2^{i * \log_2(3)}}$ is used in the proofs. ¹⁵

The following example will provide a better understanding of equation 4.44 by comparing it to 3 iterations of equation 4.4. Equations 4.43 and 4.44 will be essential for proof of the Collatz Conjecture.

¹⁵Interestingly, although not needed in this proof, it was noted that, since $b = 3 * b_{(i-1)} + 2^{(i-1)}$ $b \pmod{3} \not\equiv 0$, $b \pmod{3} \equiv 1$ if for last *Odd* Previous Step (*i*) $i \pmod{2} \equiv 1$, and $b \pmod{3} \equiv 2$ if for last *Odd* Previous Step (*i*) $i \pmod{2} \equiv 0$

Example 4.9. Equation 4.44 vs. Equation 4.4 using Ternary Parity Numbering

$$(4.44) \quad f^i(n_{\text{Original}}) = n_{\text{Step}_i} = \frac{3^P * n_{\text{Original}}}{2^i} + \frac{b}{2^i}$$

$$(4.4) \quad f(n_i) = \begin{cases} \frac{3^0 n_{(i-1)}}{2^1} + \frac{(2^0-1)}{2^1} & \text{if } n_{(i-1)} \equiv 0 \pmod{2} \text{ (Add 1 to Sequence)} \\ \frac{3^1 n_{(i-1)}}{2^1} + \frac{(2^1-1)}{2^1} & \text{if } n_{(i-1)} \equiv 1 \pmod{2} \text{ (Add 2 to Sequence)} \end{cases}$$

Step 1 2 Seq's	1	$n_1 = \left(\frac{3^0 n_O}{2^1} + \frac{(2^0-1)}{2^1}\right)^0$ $i = 1$ and $p = 0$ and $b = 0$	2	$n_1 = \left(\frac{3^1 n_O}{2^1} + \frac{(2^1-1)}{2^1}\right)^{2^0=1}$ $i = 1$ and $p = 1$ and $b = 1$
Step 2 4 Sequences	11	$n_2 = \frac{3^0 \left(\frac{3^0 n_O}{2^1} + \frac{0}{2^1}\right) + \frac{(2^0-1)}{2^1}}{2^1}$ $n_2 = \left(\frac{3^0 n_O}{2^2} + \frac{0}{2^2}\right) + \frac{0}{2^1}$ $n_2 = \left(\frac{3^0 n_O}{2^2} + \frac{0}{2^2}\right) + \frac{0}{2^2}$ $n_2 = \left(\frac{3^0 n_O}{2^2} + \frac{0+0}{2^2}\right)$ $n_2 = \left(\frac{3^0 n_O}{2^2} + \frac{0}{2^2}\right)$ $i = 2$ and $p = 0$ and $b = 0$	21	$n_2 = \frac{3^0 \left(\frac{3^1 n_O}{2^1} + \frac{1}{2^1}\right) + \frac{(2^0-1)}{2^1}}{2^1}$ $n_2 = \left(\frac{3^1 n_O}{2^2} + \frac{1}{2^2}\right) + \frac{0}{2^1}$ $n_2 = \left(\frac{3^1 n_O}{2^2} + \frac{1}{2^2}\right) + \frac{0}{2^2}$ $n_2 = \left(\frac{3^1 n_O}{2^2} + \frac{1+0}{2^2}\right)$ $n_2 = \left(\frac{3^1 n_O}{2^2} + \frac{1}{2^2}\right)$ $i = 2$ and $p = 1$ and $b = 1$
	12	$n_2 = \frac{3^1 \left(\frac{3^0 n_O}{2^1} + \frac{0}{2^1}\right) + \frac{(2^1-1)}{2^1}}{2^1}$ $n_2 = \left(\frac{3^1 n_O}{2^2} + \frac{0}{2^2}\right) + \frac{2^0}{2^1}$ $n_2 = \left(\frac{3^1 n_O}{2^2} + \frac{0}{2^2}\right) + \frac{2^1}{2^2}$ $n_2 = \left(\frac{3^1 n_O}{2^2} + \frac{0+2^1}{2^2}\right)$ $n_2 = \left(\frac{3^1 * n_O}{2^2} + \frac{2}{2^2}\right)$ $i = 2$ and $p = 1$ and $b = 2$	22	$n_2 = \frac{3^1 \left(\frac{3^1 n_O}{2^1} + \frac{1}{2^1}\right) + \frac{(2^1-1)}{2^1}}{2^1}$ $n_2 = \left(\frac{3^2 n_O}{2^2} + \frac{3}{2^2}\right) + \frac{2^0}{2^1}$ $n_2 = \left(\frac{3^2 * n_O}{2^2} + \frac{3}{2^2}\right) + \frac{2^1}{2^2}$ $n_2 = \left(\frac{3^2 * n_O}{2^2} + \frac{3+2^1}{2^2}\right)$ $n_2 = \left(\frac{3^2 * n_O}{2^2} + \frac{5}{2^2}\right)$ $i = 2$ and $p = 2$ and $b = 5$
Step 3 8 Sequences	111	$n_3 = \frac{3^0 \left(\frac{3^0 n_O}{2^2} + \frac{0}{2^2}\right) + \frac{(2^0-1)}{2^1}}{2^1}$ $n_3 = \left(\frac{3^0 n_O}{2^3} + \frac{0}{2^3}\right)$ $i = 3$ and $p = 0$ and $b = 0$	211	$n_3 = \frac{3^0 \left(\frac{3^1 n_O}{2^2} + \frac{1}{2^2}\right) + \frac{(2^0-1)}{2^1}}{2^1}$ $n_3 = \left(\frac{3^1 * n_O}{2^3} + \frac{1}{2^3}\right)$ $i = 3$ and $p = 1$ and $b = 1$
	121	$n_3 = \frac{3^0 \left(\frac{3^1 n_O}{2^2} + \frac{2}{2^2}\right) + \frac{(2^0-1)}{2^1}}{2^1}$ $n_3 = \left(\frac{3^1 n_O}{2^3} + \frac{2}{2^3}\right) + \frac{0}{2^1}$ $n_3 = \left(\frac{3^1 * n_O}{2^3} + \frac{2}{2^3}\right) + \frac{0}{2^3}$ $n_3 = \left(\frac{3^1 * n_O}{2^3} + \frac{2+0}{2^3}\right)$ $n_3 = \left(\frac{3^1 * n_O}{2^3} + \frac{2}{2^3}\right)$ $i = 3$ and $p = 1$ and $b = 2$	221	$n_3 = \frac{3^0 \left(\frac{3^2 n_O}{2^2} + \frac{5}{2^2}\right) + \frac{(2^0-1)}{2^1}}{2^1}$ $n_3 = \left(\frac{3^2 n_O}{2^3} + \frac{5}{2^3}\right) + \frac{0}{2^1}$ $n_3 = \left(\frac{3^2 * n_O}{2^3} + \frac{5}{2^3}\right) + \frac{0}{2^3}$ $n_3 = \left(\frac{3^2 * n_O}{2^3} + \frac{5+0}{2^3}\right)$ $n_3 = \left(\frac{3^2 * n_O}{2^3} + \frac{5}{2^3}\right)$ $i = 3$ and $p = 2$ and $b = 5$
	112	$n_3 = \frac{3^1 \left(\frac{3^0 n_O}{2^2} + \frac{0}{2^2}\right) + \frac{(2^1-1)}{2^1}}{2^1}$ $n_3 = \left(\frac{3^1 n_O}{2^3} + \frac{0}{2^3}\right) + \frac{2^0}{2^1}$ $n_3 = \left(\frac{3^1 n_O}{2^3} + \frac{0}{2^3}\right) + \frac{2^2}{2^3}$ $n_3 = \left(\frac{3^1 n_O}{2^3} + \frac{0+2^2}{2^3}\right)$ $n_3 = \left(\frac{3^1 n_O}{2^3} + \frac{4}{2^3}\right)$ $i = 3$ and $p = 1$ and $b = 4$	212	$n_3 = \frac{3^1 \left(\frac{3^1 n_O}{2^2} + \frac{1}{2^2}\right) + \frac{(2^1-1)}{2^1}}{2^1}$ $n_3 = \left(\frac{3^2 n_O}{2^3} + \frac{3}{2^3}\right) + \frac{2^0}{2^1}$ $n_3 = \left(\frac{3^2 n_O}{2^3} + \frac{3}{2^3}\right) + \frac{2^2}{2^3}$ $n_3 = \left(\frac{3^2 n_O}{2^3} + \frac{3+2^2}{2^3}\right)$ $n_3 = \left(\frac{3^2 n_O}{2^3} + \frac{7}{2^3}\right)$ $i = 3$ and $p = 2$ and $b = 7$
	122	$n_3 = \frac{3^1 \left(\frac{3^1 n_O}{2^2} + \frac{2}{2^2}\right) + \frac{(2^1-1)}{2^1}}{2^1}$ $n_3 = \left(\frac{3^2 n_O}{2^3} + \frac{3*2}{2^3}\right) + \frac{2^0}{2^1}$ $n_3 = \left(\frac{3^2 n_O}{2^3} + \frac{6}{2^3}\right) + \frac{2^2}{2^3}$ $n_3 = \left(\frac{3^2 n_O}{2^3} + \frac{6+2^2}{2^3}\right)$ $n_3 = \left(\frac{3^2 n_O}{2^3} + \frac{10}{2^3}\right)$ $i = 3$ and $p = 2$ and $b = 10$	222	$n_3 = \frac{3^1 \left(\frac{3^2 n_O}{2^2} + \frac{5}{2^2}\right) + \frac{(2^1-1)}{2^1}}{2^1}$ $n_3 = \left(\frac{3^3 n_O}{2^3} + \frac{3*5}{2^3}\right) + \frac{2^0}{2^1}$ $n_3 = \left(\frac{3^3 n_O}{2^3} + \frac{15}{2^3}\right) + \frac{2^2}{2^3}$ $n_3 = \left(\frac{3^3 n_O}{2^3} + \frac{15+2^2}{2^3}\right)$ $n_3 = \left(\frac{3^3 n_O}{2^3} + \frac{19}{2^3}\right)$ $i = 3$ and $p = 3$ and $b = 19$

5. IDENTICAL AND ALTERNATING EQUIVALENCE PARITY THEOREM

Theorem 5.1. For any sub-set I_j of \mathbb{N}_1 ¹⁶, where $I_j = \{n \mid j + m * 2^x \text{ where } m = \{0, 1, 2, \dots, 2^z - 1\} \text{ and } z \in \mathbb{N}_0 \text{ and } x \in \mathbb{N}_0\}$, the sample size is 2^z sequential members of the sub-set¹⁷.

Recursively applying the Short-Cut Collatz Function to all members of the sub-set will result in an exactly identical parity sequence up to and including $Step_i$ that are unique to that sub-set (at that step).

Immediately after $Step_x$ the parity of each sequential member of a sub-set will alternate. After $Step_x$ and every future step up to and including $Step_{x+z}$, exactly 50% of the resulting n_i will be Even and will rise to the next higher Energy Level at the next Step and exactly 50% of the resulting n_i will be Odd and will remain at the current Energy Level at the next Step.

When the Short-Cut Collatz function is sequentially and recursively applied forever to all members of the set, $\mathbb{N}_1 = I_1 = \{n \mid 1 + m * 2^0 \text{ where } m \in \mathbb{N}_0 \text{ and } x = 0\}$, it generates an infinite binomial distribution, resulting in a new row (r) of Pascal's Triangle¹⁸ completing every time $m = 2^r - 1$. When carried forward to infinity, each member of the set, \mathbb{N}_1 , has a unique sequence.

5.1. Identical and Alternating Equivalence Parity Theorem Proof Equation Derivation.

Proof. Any two value-less integers n_1 and n_2 that are sequential members of any sub-set I_j of \mathbb{N}_1 , where $I_j \in \{n \mid j + m * 2^x \text{ where } x \in \mathbb{N}_0 \text{ and } m \in \mathbb{N}_0\}$ may be logically represented, at $Step_0$, as:

$$n_2 = n_1 + 1 * 2^x \quad \text{and} \quad n_1 \pmod{2} \equiv n_2 \pmod{2}$$

since all sequential integers in the sub-set are exactly 2^x apart. A proof for any two value-less sequential members of any sub-set I_j is sufficient to prove the theorem.¹⁹

At $Step_i$, where $i \leq x$ and “(I/A)” = Identical/Alternating $\pmod{2}$ variable, where Identical Parity = 0 and Alternating Parity = 1:

Using Equation 4.44:

$$f(n_1)_{Step\ i} = \frac{(3^p * n_1 + b_1)}{2^i}$$

$$f(n_2)_{Step\ i} = \frac{(3^p * n_2 + b_2)}{2^i} = \frac{(3^p * (n_1 + 1 * 2^x) + b_2)}{2^i}$$

Using Simplified Distributive Property of Parity $_{\pmod{2}}$ for Subtraction:

$$(f(n_2)_{Step\ i} - f(n_1)_{Step\ i}) \pmod{2} \equiv \left| f(n_2)_{Step\ i} \pmod{2} - f(n_1)_{Step\ i} \pmod{2} \right|$$

$$\therefore (f(n_2)_{Step\ i} - f(n_1)_{Step\ i}) \pmod{2} \equiv (I/A)$$

¹⁶Defined in Sub-Section 4.4

¹⁷Sample size is critical for 50% Alternating Parity Theorem not Identical Parity Theorem

¹⁸of Reduced Fractional Numerators $N_{LStep\ i}$ (Sub-subsection 4.19.1)

¹⁹A proof is also possible for any two value-less members of any sub-set I_j where $m_{n_1} \pmod{2} \neq m_{n_2} \pmod{2}$ but the sequential member proof is more intuitive and straight-forward.

Substitute:

$$\left(\frac{(3^p * (n_1 + 1 * 2^x) + b_2)}{2^i} - \frac{(3^p * n_1 + b_1)}{2^i} \right) \pmod{2} \equiv (I/A)$$

Simplify:

$$\left((3^p * 2^{x-i}) + \frac{b_2 - b_1}{2^i} \right) \pmod{2} \equiv (I/A)$$

(Using Function 4.45, it is clear that, until $n_{1_i} \pmod{2} \neq n_{2_i} \pmod{2}$, that $b_1 = b_2$.)

If:

$$(3^p * 2^{(x-i)}) \pmod{2} \equiv 0 \text{ then } n_{1_i} \pmod{2} \equiv n_{2_i} \pmod{2} \text{ after Step}_i$$

$$(3^p * 2^{(x-i)}) \pmod{2} \equiv 1 \text{ then } n_{1_i} \pmod{2} \neq n_{2_i} \pmod{2} \text{ after Step}_i$$

5.2. Case 1 ($i \leq x - 1$) Proof Evaluation.

Where: $i \leq x - 1$

$$\begin{aligned} x - i &\geq 1 \\ 2^{(x-i)} \pmod{2} &\equiv 0 \\ 3^p \pmod{2} &\equiv 1 \text{(Power of 3)} \end{aligned}$$

Evaluating:

$$\begin{aligned} 3^p * 2^{(x-i)} \\ \text{Odd} * \text{Even} \\ \therefore (3^p * 2^{(x-i)}) \pmod{2} &\equiv 0 \end{aligned}$$

\therefore **Case 1** results in $n_{1_{(x-1)}} \pmod{2} \equiv n_{2_{(x-1)}} \pmod{2}$ with **Identical Parity Sequences** up to and including Step_x.

5.3. Case 2 ($i = x$) Proof Evaluation.

Where: $i = x$

$$\begin{aligned} x - i &= 0 \\ 2^{(x-i)} \pmod{2} &\equiv 1 \\ 3^p \pmod{2} &\equiv 1 \text{(Power of 3)} \end{aligned}$$

Evaluating:

$$\begin{aligned} 3^p * 2^{(x-i)} \\ \text{Odd} * \text{Odd} \\ \therefore (3^p * 2^{(x-i)}) \pmod{2} &\equiv 1 \end{aligned}$$

\therefore **Case 2** results in $n_{1_{(x)}} \pmod{2} \neq n_{2_{(x)}} \pmod{2}$ after Step_x and with an **Alternating Parity Sequence** at Step_(x+1).

5.4. Case 3 ($i = x$) and $n_3 = n_1 + 2 * 2^x$ Proof Evaluation.

The next value-less sequential member (n_3) of the sub-set I_j may be logically represented as:

$$n_3 = n_1 + 2 * 2^x$$

Where: $i = x$

$$x - i = 0$$

$$2^{(x-i)} \pmod{2} \equiv 1$$

$$3^p \pmod{2} \equiv 1_{(\text{Power of 3})}$$

Evaluating:

$$3^p * 2 * 2^{(x-i)}$$

$$\text{Odd} * \text{Even} * \text{Odd}$$

$$\therefore (3^p * 2 * 2^{(x-i)}) \pmod{2} \equiv 0$$

\therefore **Case 3** results in $n_{1(x)} \pmod{2} \equiv n_{3(x)} \pmod{2}$ after Step_x and with an **Identical Parity Sequences** up to and including $\text{Step}_{(x+1)}$.

It is therefore proved that, all members of any sub-set I_j will follow an Identical Parity Sequence up to Step_x that is independent of $m \pmod{2}$. It is also proved that, at Step_{x+1} , members of the sub-set, where $m \pmod{2} \equiv 1$ will have an Alternate Parity Sequence at Step_{x+1} to members of the sub-set, where $m \pmod{2} \equiv 0$.

Although the parity of any particular integer, at each step after Step_{x+1} , seems chaotic and is initially difficult to determine, the exactability of the 50% evenly split parities is proven for all steps after Step_x up to and including Step_{x+z} , provided the sample size is a positive integer power of 2 of sequential members of a sub-set I_j .

This exactability is easily and logically explained by the understanding that after Step_x this particular sub-set must be Equally Partitioned into two new sub-sets (I_j) where the value of new value x increments to becomes $x + 1$ and maintains an identical parity sequence for those new sub-sets at **only** the next step, after which it must be Equally Partitioned again.

This process will continue ad infinitum, revealing the true nature of the Short-cut Collatz function as a pure binomial expansion. When the Short-Cut Collatz function is sequentially and recursively applied forever to all members of the set, $\mathbb{N}_1 = I_1 = \{n \mid 1 + m * 2^0 \text{ where } m \in \mathbb{N}_0 \text{ and } x = 0\}$, it generates an infinite binomial distribution, resulting in a new row (r) of Pascal's Triangle¹⁸ completing every time $m = 2^r - 1$. When carried forward to infinity, each member of the set, \mathbb{N}_1 , has a unique sequence.

Since any sub-set I_j can be infinitely Evenly Partitioned, this proof extends to infinity. Therefore, the Identical and Alternating Equivalence Parity Theorem is true. \square

6. EV GREATER THAN $(\log_2(3) - 1)$ THEOREM

Theorem 6.1. For every $n_O \in \mathbb{N}_1$, the first time $EV > (\log_2(3) - 1)$, then $n_i \leq n_O$. For $n_O = 1$, the first time $EV > (\log_2(3) - 1)$, then $n_i = n_O = 1$, starting the only known Shortcut Collatz Function terminal loop $\{1, 2, 1, 2, \dots \infty\}$. All other $n_O \in \mathbb{N}_1 > 1$ will result in $n_i < n_O$ or a very slight possibility, which

will be eliminated in the next theorem, that $n_i = n_O$, which would start a previously undiscovered terminal loop, if such existed.

Proof. Proof for *Even* Integers is intuitive since $n_i < n_O$ after the first step and $EV = \frac{q}{p} = \frac{1}{0} \gg (\log_2(3) - 1)$ (*Undefined*).

6.1. Energy Value $> (\log_2(3) - 1)$ Theorem Proof Equation Derivation.
Proof for *Odd* n_O provided by evaluating 3 Cases plus Special Case for next theorem where:

$$EV + v = \log_2(3) - 1$$

Case 1: $EV = \log_2(3) - 1$ where $(v = 0)$

Case 2: $EV < \log_2(3) - 1$ where $(v > 0)$

Case 3: $EV > \log_2(3) - 1$ where $(v < 0)$

Special Case 4: $EV > \log_2(3) - 1$ where $(v < 0$ and $w = 0)$

Substituting and rearranging $EV + v = \log_2(3) - 1$, where $EV = \frac{q}{p}$ yields:

$$q = p * \log_2(3) - p - v * p$$

Using Equation 4.42:

$$n_O + w = \frac{3^p * n_O}{2^i} + \frac{b}{2^i}$$

Where:

i = Total Number of Steps

p = Number of Odd Steps

q = Number of Even Steps

$\frac{q}{p} = EV =$ Energy Value ($0 \leq EV \leq \infty_{\text{[undefined]}}$)

$$2^i = 2^{(p+q)} = 2^p * 2^q$$

Substituting:

$$n_O + w = \frac{3^p * n_O}{2^p * 2^q} + \frac{b}{2^p * 2^q} = \frac{3^p * n_O}{2^p * 2^{p * \log_2(3) - p - v * p}} + \frac{b}{2^p * 2^{p * \log_2(3) - p - v * p}}$$

Condensing, rearranging and cancelling since $\frac{3^p}{2^{p * \log_2(3)}} = \frac{3^p}{3^p} = 1$:

$$\begin{aligned} n_O + w &= \frac{3^p * n_O}{2^{p * \log_2(3)} * 2^{-v * p}} + \frac{b}{2^{p * \log_2(3)} * 2^{-v * p}} \\ n_O + w &= \left(\frac{3^p}{2^{p * \log_2(3)}} * 2^{v * p} * n_O \right) + \left(\frac{b}{2^{p * \log_2(3)}} * 2^{v * p} \right) \\ n_O + w &= \left(2^{v * p} * n_O \right) + \left(\frac{b}{2^{p * \log_2(3)}} * 2^{v * p} \right) \end{aligned}$$

Subtract n_O from both sides:

$$w = \left(2^{v * p} * n_O \right) - n_O + \left(\frac{b}{2^{p * \log_2(3)}} * 2^{v * p} \right)$$

Factor out n_O :

$$w = \left(2^{v * p} - 1 \right) * n_O + \left(\frac{b}{2^{p * \log_2(3)}} * 2^{v * p} \right)$$

Simplify by substitution:

$$w = (V - 1) * n_O + B * V = R * n_O + B * V$$

Where:

$$B = \frac{b}{2^{p * \log_2(3)}} = \begin{cases} \frac{1}{3} \leq B < 1 \therefore B = \text{Positive } \frac{\text{Proper}}{\text{Fraction}} & \text{if } n_O \pmod{2} \equiv 1 \\ 0 \leq B < 1 \therefore B = 0 \text{ or Positive } \frac{\text{Proper}}{\text{Fraction}} & \text{if } n_O \pmod{2} \equiv 0 \end{cases}$$

$$V = 2^{v * p} = \begin{cases} 2^{0 * p} = 1 \therefore V = 1 & \text{if } v = 0 \\ 2^{(>0) * p} > 1 \therefore V > 1 & \text{if } v > 0 \\ 0 < \frac{1}{2^{|v| * p}} < 1 \therefore V = \text{Positive } \frac{\text{Proper}}{\text{Fraction}} & \text{if } v < 0 \end{cases}$$

$$R = V - 1 = \begin{cases} 1 - 1 = 0 \therefore R = 0 & \text{if } v = 0 \\ (> 1) - 1 \therefore R > 0 & \text{if } v > 0 \\ (> 0) - 1 < R < (< 1) - 1 \therefore R = \text{Negative } \frac{\text{Proper}}{\text{Fraction}} & \text{if } v < 0 \end{cases}$$

6.2. Case 1 ($v = 0$) Proof Evaluation.

For $n_O \pmod{2} \equiv 1$ where:

$$\begin{aligned} B &= \text{Positive } \frac{\text{Proper}}{\text{Fraction}} \\ V &= 1 \\ R &= 0 \end{aligned}$$

Given $w = R * n_O + B * V$:

$$\begin{aligned} w &= 0 * n_{\text{Original}} + B * 1 \\ w &= B \end{aligned}$$

This is not possible since:

$$\begin{aligned} B &\text{ is a Positive } \frac{\text{Proper}}{\text{Fraction}} \\ w &= \text{Integer} \\ \therefore w &\neq B \text{ and } v \neq 0 \text{ and } EV = \frac{q}{p} \neq \log_2(3) - 1 \end{aligned}$$

\therefore For Case 1 where $v = 0$

NOT POSSIBLE

6.3. Case 2 ($v > 0$) Proof Evaluation.

For $n_O \pmod{2} \equiv 1$ where:

$$\begin{aligned} B &= \text{Positive } \frac{\text{Proper}}{\text{Fraction}} \\ V &> 1 \\ R &> 0 \end{aligned}$$

Given $w = R * n_O + B * V$:

$$\begin{aligned} w &= (> 0) * n_O + B * (> 1) \\ w &> 0 \text{ but since } w = \text{Integer then} \\ w &\geq 1 \end{aligned}$$

∴ For Case 2 where $v > 0$

$$n_i > n_O$$

6.4. Case 3 ($v < 0$) Proof Evaluation.

For $n_O \pmod{2} \equiv 1$ where:

$$\begin{aligned} B &= \text{Positive } \frac{\text{Proper}}{\text{Fraction}} \\ V &= \text{Positive } \frac{\text{Proper}}{\text{Fraction}} \\ R &= \text{Negative } \frac{\text{Proper}}{\text{Fraction}} \end{aligned}$$

Given $w = R * n_O + B * V$:

$$R * n_O = \text{Negative } \frac{\text{Proper}}{\text{Fraction}} * n_O = \text{Negative Fraction (Possibly } \frac{\text{Proper}}{\text{Fraction}})$$

$$B * V = \text{Positive } \frac{\text{Proper}}{\text{Fraction}} * \text{Positive } \frac{\text{Proper}}{\text{Fraction}} = \text{Positive } \frac{\text{Proper}}{\text{Fraction}}$$

$$w = \text{Negative Fraction (Possibly } \frac{\text{Proper}}{\text{Fraction}}) + \text{Positive } \frac{\text{Proper}}{\text{Fraction}}$$

$$\therefore w \leq 0$$

∴ For Case 3 where $v < 0$

$$n_i < n_O \text{ or starts a Terminal Loop}$$

6.5. Proof is provided by Case1, Case 2 and Case 3.

Therefore, the Energy Value $> (\log_2(3) - 1)$ Theorem is true. \square

6.6. Special Case 4 ($v < 0$ and $w = 0$) Proof Evaluation.

Since (from Case 3):

$$w = \text{Negative Fraction (Possibly } \frac{\text{Proper}}{\text{Fraction}}) + \text{Positive } \frac{\text{Proper}}{\text{Fraction}}$$

$w = 0$ only if:

$$|R * n_O| = |\text{Negative } \underline{\text{Must Be}} \frac{\text{Proper}}{\text{Fraction}}| = \text{Positive } \frac{\text{Proper}}{\text{Fraction}}$$

Then the following must be true:

$$-1 < R * n_O < 0$$

$$-1 < (V - 1) * n_O < 0$$

$$-1 < \left(\frac{1}{2^{|v|*p}} - 1\right) * n_O < 0$$

$$\frac{-1}{n_O} < \frac{1}{2^{|v|*p}} - 1$$

$$\text{(Invert and Multiply by -1)} \quad n_O < \frac{-1}{\frac{1}{2^{|v|*p}} - 1} \quad \text{(Reverses inequality and back again)}$$

$$n_O \leq \left\lfloor \frac{-1}{\frac{1}{2^{|v|*p}} - 1} \right\rfloor \quad \text{(Floor to account for integer values)}$$

∴ ONLY IF $n_O \leq \left\lfloor \frac{-1}{\frac{1}{2^{|v|*p}} - 1} \right\rfloor$ does there exists a **possibility** that any terminal loop sequence restarts at Step_{*i*}. This will be used in the next theorem and proof that there are no other terminal loop sequences than the known one $\{1, 2, 1, 2, \dots \infty\}$.

7. NO TERMINAL LOOP OTHER THAN (1,2,1,2, ... INFINITY) THEOREM

Theorem 7.1. *There are no terminal loop sequences possible other than the known terminal loop sequence $\{1, 2, 1, 2, \dots \infty\}$.*

Proof of this theorem will eliminate the very slight possibility that $n_i = n_O$ for $n_O \in \mathbb{N}_1 > 1$ discovered in the Proof of the Energy Value $> (\log_2(3) - 1)$ Theorem.

Proof. For any possible terminal loop sequence, the following should be considered given, intuitive, logical or already proven:

- It must have identical repeating sequence steps with sequence length i .
- It must have identical repeating values such that:
 - $n_O = n_i$
 - $n_{O+1} = n_{i+1}$
 - $n_{O+2} = n_{i+2}$
 - \vdots
 - $n_i = n_{2*i}$
- Any value in the loop must be able to serve as n_O
 - Calculating EV starting at any n_O in the loop results in
 - * $EV > (\log_2(3) - 1)$ after Step $_i$
- If loop is started with the lowest value n_O in the loop
 - $n_O \pmod{2} \equiv 1$
 - $n_{i-1} \pmod{2} \equiv 0$
- With each complete repetition (r) of any loop with sequence length i
 - The absolute value of v ($|v|$), will remain the same since the ratio of Even to Odd Steps (EV) will remain the same.
 - The value of p will increase by a multiple of r since ALL the Steps have increased by a multiple of r .
 - Multiple repetitions of a loop are, by definition, a loop also.
 - * For example the value sequences below are functionally equivalent but will provide different mathematical answers, prior to the Floor Function, when used in the proof equation from Energy Value $> (\log_2(3) - 1)$ Theorem Special Case 4.
 - (1, 2) of period 2
 - (1, 2, 1, 2) of period 4
 - (1, 2, 1, 2, 1, 2) of period 6
 - (1, 2, 1, 2, 1, 2, 1, 2) of period 8
- All values of n_O in the loop with sequence length i
 - Must satisfy the requirements of:
 - * Energy Value $> (\log_2(3) - 1)$ Theorem Special Case 4

$$n_O \leq \left\lfloor \frac{-1}{2^{|v|*p} - 1} \right\rfloor \text{ at Step}_i$$

With ∞ repetitions of any possible loop, $|v|$ will remain constant while p will increase towards ∞ and eventually $\left\lfloor \frac{-1}{2^{|v|*p} - 1} \right\rfloor = 1$. Therefore there is only one possible Shortcut Collatz Function terminal loop sequence $\{1, 2, 1, 2, \dots \infty\}$ and the No Terminal Loop Sequence other than $\{1, 2, 1, 2, \dots \infty\}$ Theorem is true. \square

8. EL GREATER THAN/EQUAL TO $\log_2(n_O) + p(\log_2(3) - 1)$ THEOREM

Theorem 8.1. For every $n_O \in \mathbb{N}_1$, the first time $EL \geq \log_2(n_O) + p * (\log_2(3) - 1)$, then $n_{Step_i} = 1$.²⁰

Proof. First a mathematical proof with 3 case evaluations will be presented followed by a logical discussion and evaluation.

8.1. **Energy Level $\geq \log_2(n_O) + p * (\log_2(3) - 1)$ Theorem Proof Equation Derivation.** Proof for both $n_O \pmod{2} \equiv 1$ and $n_O \pmod{2} \equiv 0$ will be provided by evaluating 3 Cases where $EL + v = \log_2(n_O) + p * (\log_2(3) - 1)$.

Case 1: $EL > \log_2(n_O) + p * (\log_2(3) - 1)$ where $(v < 0)$

Case 2: $EL = \log_2(n_O) + p * (\log_2(3) - 1)$ where $(v = 0)$

Case 3: $EL < \log_2(n_O) + p * (\log_2(3) - 1)$ where $(v > 0)$

Using Equation 4.42:

$$n_i = n_O + w = \frac{3^p * n_O}{2^i} + \frac{b}{2^i}$$

Where:

$i =$ Total Number of Steps

$p =$ Number of Odd Steps

$EL = q =$ Number of Even Steps

$$2^i = 2^{(p+q)} = 2^p * 2^q$$

And where $v =$ value required to complete equivalence:

$$q + v = \log_2(n_O) + p * (\log_2(3) - 1)$$

$$q = \log_2(n_O) + p * (\log_2(3) - 1) - v$$

$$q = \log_2(n_O) + p * (\log_2(3)) - p - v$$

Substituting, Condensing and Rearranging:

$$n_O + w = \frac{3^p * n_O}{2^p * 2^q} + \frac{b}{2^p * 2^q}$$

$$n_O + w = \frac{3^p * n_O + b}{2^p * 2^{\log_2(n_O) + p * (\log_2(3)) - p - v}}$$

$$n_O + w = \frac{3^p * n_O + b}{2^{\log_2(n_O)} * 2^{p * (\log_2(3))} * 2^{-v}}$$

$$n_O + w = \frac{3^p * n_O + b}{n_O * 3^p * 2^{-v}}$$

$$n_O + w = \frac{3^p * n_O}{n_O * 3^p * 2^{-v}} + \frac{b}{n_O * 3^p * 2^{-v}}$$

$$n_O + w = 2^v + \frac{b * 2^v}{n_O * 3^p} = 2^v + \frac{2^v}{n_O} * \frac{b}{3^p}$$

$$n_O + w = 2^v + \frac{2^v}{n_O} * \left(0 \text{ or Positive } \frac{\text{Proper}}{\text{Fraction}} \right) \quad \text{Since } 0 \leq \frac{b}{3^p} < 1$$

²⁰The same logic applies to $EV > \frac{\log_2(n_O)}{p} + (\log_2(3) - 1)$ but Energy Level is used here for use with plot where the y -axis is the number of *Even* steps (Energy Levels) and the x -axis is the number of *Odd* steps.

8.2. Case 1 ($v < 0$) Proof Evaluation.

Since $v < 0$ then $n_O + w = 2^v + \frac{2^v}{n_O} * \left(0 \text{ or Positive } \frac{\text{Proper}}{\text{Fraction}} \right)$ becomes:

$$\begin{aligned} n_O + w &= \frac{1}{2^{|v|}} + \frac{1}{2^{|v|} * n_O} * \left(0 \text{ or Positive } \frac{\text{Proper}}{\text{Fraction}} \right) \\ n_O + w &= \text{Positive } \frac{\text{Proper}}{\text{Fraction}} + \text{Positive } \frac{\text{Proper}}{\text{Fraction}} * \left(0 \text{ or Positive } \frac{\text{Proper}}{\text{Fraction}} \right) \\ 0 &< n_O + w < 2 \end{aligned}$$

$$n_i = n_O + w = 1 \text{ (Since } n_O \in \mathbb{N}_1 \text{ and } w \text{ is an integer [} w = 1 - n_O \text{])}$$

∴ **For Case 1 where $v < 0$**

If the Energy Level $> \log_2(n_O) + p * (\log_2(3) - 1)$, then $n_i = 1$.

8.3. Case 2 ($v = 0$) Proof Evaluation.

Since $v = 0$ then $n_O + w = 2^v + \frac{2^v}{n_O} * \left(0 \text{ or Positive } \frac{\text{Proper}}{\text{Fraction}} \right)$ becomes:

$$\begin{aligned} n_O + w &= 2^0 + \frac{2^0}{n_O} * \left(0 \text{ or Positive } \frac{\text{Proper}}{\text{Fraction}} \right) \\ n_O + w &= 1 + \text{Positive } \frac{\text{Proper}}{\text{Fraction}} * \left(0 \text{ or Positive } \frac{\text{Proper}}{\text{Fraction}} \right) \\ 1 &\leq n_O + w < 2 \end{aligned}$$

$$n_i = n_O + w = 1 \text{ (Since } n_O \in \mathbb{N}_1 \text{ and } w \text{ is an integer [} w = 1 - n_O \text{])}$$

∴ **For Case 2 where $v = 0$**

If the Energy Level $= \log_2(n_O) + p * (\log_2(3) - 1)$, then $n_i = 1$.

8.4. Case 3 ($v > 0$) Proof Evaluation.

Since $v > 0$ then $n_O + w = 2^v + \frac{2^v}{n_O} * \left(0 \text{ or Positive } \frac{\text{Proper}}{\text{Fraction}} \right)$ becomes:

$$\begin{aligned} n_O + w &= 2^{(>0)} + \frac{2^{(>0)}}{n_O} * \left(0 \text{ or Positive } \frac{\text{Proper}}{\text{Fraction}} \right) \\ n_O + w &= (> 1) + \frac{\text{Positive Fraction}}{\text{Possibly Proper}} * \left(0 \text{ or Positive } \frac{\text{Proper}}{\text{Fraction}} \right) \\ n_O + w &= (> 1) + \frac{\text{Positive Fraction}}{\text{Possibly Proper}} \\ 1 &< n_O + w \end{aligned}$$

$$n_i = n_O + w \geq 2 \text{ (Since } n_O \in \mathbb{N}_1 \text{ and } w \text{ is an integer [} w \geq 1 \text{])}$$

∴ **For Case 3 where $v > 0$**

If the Energy Level $< \log_2(n_O) + p * (\log_2(3) - 1)$, then $n_i \geq 2$.

8.5. Logical Proof Discussion and Evaluation. The evidence of this proof depends on proper logical evaluation of the Unequally partitioned FINITE Sub-sets (F_j) of \mathbb{N}_1 where the members of each sub-set, are: ²¹

$$F_j = \begin{cases} \{n \mid n = 1\} & \text{if } j = 0 \\ \{n \mid 2^{j-1} + 1 \leq n \leq 2^j\} & \text{if } j \geq 1 \end{cases}$$

Evidence for this theorem and it's proof first appeared when plotting the sequence of Short-cut function steps for different sub-sets of the positive starting integers, where the y -axis is the number of *Even* steps and the x -axis is the number of *Odd* steps. It became strongly evident, that, when plotting the first time that the integers in a sequence became equal to one, there was a well defined straight-line upper limit with a $slope = p * \log_2(3) - 1$, by which all integers tested had become equal to one.

After many of the Infinite FINITE Sub-sets (F_j), were plotted it became evident that each FINITE Sub-set had its own straight-line upper limit $= y_1 + p * (\log_2(3) - 1)$ and its own straight-line lower limit $= y_2 + p * (\log_2(3) - 1)$. All $n_O \in F_j$ solved to $n_i \in F_0 = 1$ between these limits. It was noted that $y_2 < j < y_1$ and that $y_1 - y_2 \approx 1$.²²

On closer examination of the data for different Sub-sets (F_j), it became obvious that converting the straight-line limit equations to a ceiling function would generate the Irregular Sub-set F_0 Membership Line. This equation is called the One Energy Level (*OEL*) Equation 4.21

$$OEL = \lceil \log_2(n_O) + p * (\log_2(3) - 1) \rceil$$

At this point, it was necessary to take a step back and re-examine the previous Energy Value $> (\log_2(3) - 1)$ Theorem and Proof.

Intuitively, it is obvious that, as soon as $n_i < n_O$, then the EV Ratio Calculation, for the next "less than", would need to start again with n_i as the NEW $n_{O_{New}}$. While this is true, it does not directly lead to a proof that:

$$\text{The first time: } EL_{n_i} \geq \log_2(n_O) + p * (\log_2(3) - 1) \text{ then: } n_i = 1$$

since there are many $n_O \in F_j$ that will solve to $n_i < n_O$ but where n_i is *still* a member of Sub-set F_j . This becomes more probable with higher values of j as the size of the Sub-sets F_j grow, with integers at the higher end of the Sub-set having more opportunities to result in $n_i \in F_j < n_O \in F_j$.

Instead, it is necessary to evaluate n_O and it's subsequent sequential n_i based on the *first time* that *ONE* of the n_i becomes a member of *EACH* of the FINITE Sub-sets (F_q) where:

$$f(F_q) = \lceil \log_2(n_O) + p * (\log_2(3) - 1) \rceil - q$$

Where: $n_O \in F_j$

and: $p \in \{0, 1, 2, \dots, \text{until NEWFIRST } n_i \in F_0 = 1\}$

and: $q \in \{0 \leq q \leq j\}$

²¹Defined in Sub-Section 4.5

²²Note, again, that $j = \lceil \log_2(n_O \in F_j) \rceil$.

It is not possible, using the Short-cut Collatz function, for $n_i \in F_q$ to become $n_{i_{plus}} \in F_{q-1}$ ²³ without first being $n_{(i_{plus}-1)} \in F_q \pmod{2} \equiv 0$, since there is a One-to-One relation between all $n_{i_{plus}} \in F_{q-1}$ and $n_{(i_{plus}-1)} \in F_q \pmod{2} \equiv 0$.

In order to reach $n_{i_{plus}} \in F_0$, whose only member is 1, the sequence for $n_O \in F_j$ MUST sequentially pass through all intervening Sub-sets $\{F_j, F_{(j-1)}, F_{(j-2)}, \dots, F_0\}$.

Until any $n_i \in F_q$ has first become $n_{i_{plus}} \in F_{(q-1)}$, any $\text{Step}_{i_{plus}}$, after which $n_{i_{plus}} \notin F_q$ or $n_{i_{plus}} \in F_q \pmod{2} \equiv 1$, is *trivial* even if $n_{i_{plus}} < n_i$. The only *non-trivial* $\text{Step}_{i_{plus}}$ would be the $\text{Step}_{i_{plus}}$, after which, $n_i \in F_q$ first becomes $n_{i_{plus}} \in F_{(q-1)}$. This *non-trivial* $\text{Step}_{i_{plus}}$ will always occur after the *trivial* $\text{Step}_{(i_{plus}-1)}$ where $n_{(i_{plus}-1)}$ is the *FIRST* $n_{i_{plus}} \in F_{(q)} \pmod{2} \equiv 0$.

A very clear and highly accurate picture of this process is provided by Figure 3, which plots the Irregular Finite Sub-set Membership Lines from F_j to F_0 for $n_O = 359$ using Function 4.22. Note that these function generated Irregular Finite Sub-set Membership Lines are specific for and must be generated for each n_O .

As can be seen, each Irregular Finite Sub-set Membership Line is separated from those above and below it, if they exist²⁴, by exactly 1 *Even* step (q) at each *Odd* step (p), ensuring that all points in a sequence, unless $n_{i_{plus}} \in F_{j_{plus}}$ or $n_{i_{plus}}$ has previously become $n_{i_{plus}} \in F_0$, will fall on *one and only one* of the lines and the sequence point *will* be a member of the associated Finite Sub-set F_q .

When any $n_{i_{plus}} \in F_q$ first becomes $n_{i_{plus}} \in F_{q-1}$:

- If $n_{i_{plus}} \in F_{q-1} \pmod{2} \equiv 0$, immediately after the next $\text{Step}_{(i_{plus}+1)}$, which is *non-trivial*, it will become the *FIRST* $n_{i_{plus}} \in F_{q-2}$.
- If $n_{i_{plus}} \in F_{q-1} \pmod{2} \equiv 1$, for all future $\text{Steps}_{(i_{plus})}$, which are *trivial*, its Sub-set memberships will be limited to $n_{i_{plus}} \in F_{(q-1)_{plus}}$ until it becomes $n_{i_{plus}} \in F_{q-1} \pmod{2} \equiv 0$, after which it will, immediately, after the next $\text{Step}_{(i_{plus}+1)}$, which is *non-trivial*, become the *FIRST* $n_{i_{plus}} \in F_{q-2}$.
 - The path for the first $n_{i_{plus}} \in F_{q-1} \pmod{2} \equiv 1$ to reach $n_{i_{plus}} \in F_{q-1} \pmod{2} \equiv 0$ may be very long and convoluted or very short and direct.
 - The path may result in a multitude of instances where $n_{i_{plus}} < n_i$, or even $n_{i_{plus}} < n_O$, and may return to where $n_{i_{plus}} \in F_q$ or $F_{q_{plus}}$ multiple times.
 - All steps are *trivial* until the *FIRST* $n_{i_{plus}} \in F_{q-1} \pmod{2} \equiv 0$
- Recursive application of the Identical and Alternating Equivalence Parity Theorem and Energy Value $> (\log_2(3)-1)$ Theorem Proofs ensures that for all $n_i \in F_q$ there MUST exist a $\text{Step}_{i_{plus}}$ where $n_{i_{plus}} \in F_{q-1}$ and that for all $n_O \in F_j$ there MUST exist a total of j *non-trivial* $\text{Steps}_{i_{plus}}$ that MUST be sequentially passed through to become a member of all intervening Sub-sets $\{F_j, F_{j-1}, F_{j-2}, \dots, F_0\}$, until finally reaching $n_{i_{plus}} \in F_0$, whose only member is 1.

Example 8.2. First, a thought experiment to determine the lowest number of *non-trivial* $\text{Steps}_{i_{plus}}$ that an $n_O \in F_j$ must pass through to become $n_{i_{plus}} \in F_q = F_0 = 1$ for a particular Finite Sub-set(F_j), in this case:

²³The sub-script *plus* is used hereafter to designate that a current value-less variable is greater than the original value-less variable. For example, $i_{plus} > i$, $j_{plus} > j$ and $q_{plus} > q$.

²⁴Lines and Equation are not needed and can be inaccurate where $q > j$ or $q < 0$ or after $n_i = 1$ the first time.

$$F_5 \in \{n \mid 2^{5-1} + 1 \leq n \leq 2^5\}$$

$$F_5 \in \{17, 18, 19, 20, 21, 22, 23, 24, 25, 26, 27, 28, 29, 30, 31, 32\}$$

The shortest path to 1 is for $n_O = 32$ which will undergo 5 *Even* steps and 0 *Odd* steps before $n_{i_{plus}} = 1$. Each $n_{i_{plus}} \in F_q$ is *Even* and the EV would be undefined since there are no *Odd* steps and $\frac{q}{p} = \frac{5}{0} = \text{Undefined}$.

$$32 \in F_5 \in \{n \mid 2^{5-1} + 1 \leq n \leq 2^5\} \quad (\text{Divide by 2 to next lower Finite Sub-Set})$$

$$16 \in F_4 \in \{n \mid 2^{4-1} + 1 \leq n \leq 2^4\} \quad (\text{Divide by 2 to next lower Finite Sub-Set})$$

$$8 \in F_3 \in \{n \mid 2^{3-1} + 1 \leq n \leq 2^3\} \quad (\text{Divide by 2 to next lower Finite Sub-Set})$$

$$4 \in F_2 \in \{n \mid 2^{2-1} + 1 \leq n \leq 2^2\} \quad (\text{Divide by 2 to next lower Finite Sub-Set})$$

$$2 \in F_1 \in \{n \mid 2^{1-1} + 1 \leq n \leq 2^1\} \quad (\text{Divide by 2 to next lower Finite Sub-Set})$$

$$1 \in F_0 \in \{n \mid n = 1\} \quad (q = 5 = j = \text{non-trivial Steps}_{i_{plus}})$$

Example 8.3. Next we will examine the progress of the sequence generated by $n_O = 359$, which is plotted in Figures 2 and 3 and is a member of the Sub-set F_9

$$359 \in F_9 \in \{n \mid 2^{9-1} + 1 \leq n \leq 2^9\}$$

whose Irregular Finite Sub-set Membership Line is generated by:

$$f(F_9) = \lceil \log_2(359) + p * (\log_2(3) - 1) \rceil - 9$$

The sequence for $n_O = 359$ travels below the Irregular Finite Sub-set Membership Line for Sub-set F_8 in Figure 3.

$$f(F_8) = \lceil \log_2(359) + p * (\log_2(3) - 1) \rceil - 8$$

for 10 *Odd* steps and 6 *Even* steps until $n_{i_{plus}} = 325$, which is *still* a member of Sub-set F_9 and is *Odd*. These steps are all *trivial* even though $325 < 359$.

$$325 \in F_9 \in \{n \mid 2^{9-1} + 1 \leq n \leq 2^9\}$$

The sequence past $n_{i_{plus}} = 325$ also travels below the Irregular Finite Sub-set Membership Line for Sub-set F_8 in Figure 3.

$$f(F_8) = \lceil \log_2(359) + p * (\log_2(3) - 1) \rceil - 8$$

for 1 *Odd* step until $n_{i_{plus}} = 488$ ($488 > 359 > 325$), which is *again* a member of Sub-set F_9 but is *Even*. This step could be considered *semi-trivial* since it resulted in a *FIRST* $n_{i_{plus}} \in F_9 \pmod{2} \equiv 0$.

$$488 \in F_9 \in \{n \mid 2^{9-1} + 1 \leq n \leq 2^9\}$$

Since $n_{i_{plus}} = 488$ is *Even* it will immediately be divided by 2 to become the $244 = \text{FIRST } n_{i_{plus}} \in F_8$ and the *FIRST* $n_{i_{plus}} \in F_8 \pmod{2} \equiv 0$. It plots on the Irregular Finite Sub-set Membership Line for Sub-set F_8 in Figure 3. This is a *non-trivial* step.

$$244 \in F_8 \in \{n \mid 2^{8-1} + 1 \leq n \leq 2^8\}$$

Since $n_{i_{plus}} = 244$ is *Even* it will immediately be divided by 2 to become the $122 = \text{FIRST } n_{i_{plus}} \in F_7$ and the *FIRST* $n_{i_{plus}} \in F_7 \pmod{2} \equiv 0$. It plots on the Irregular Finite Sub-set Membership Line for Sub-set F_7 in Figure 3. This is a *non-trivial* step.

$$122 \in F_7 \in \{n \mid 2^{7-1} + 1 \leq n \leq 2^7\}$$

Since $n_{i_{plus}} = 122$ is *Even* it will immediately be divided by 2 to become the $61 = \text{FIRST } n_{i_{plus}} \in F_6$ and is *Odd*. It plots on the Irregular Finite Sub-set Membership Line for Sub-set F_6 in Figure 3. This is a *non-trivial* step.

$$61 \in F_6 \in \{n \mid 2^{6-1} + 1 \leq n \leq 2^6\}$$

Since $n_{i_{plus}} = 61$ is *Odd*, the sequence past $n_{i_{plus}} = 61$ will travel below the Irregular Finite Sub-set Membership Line for Sub-set F_5 in Figure 3.

$$f(F_5) = \lceil \log_2(359) + p * (\log_2(3) - 1) \rceil - 5$$

for 1 *Odd* step and 1 *Even* step until $n_{i_{plus}} = 46$, which is *still* a member of Sub-set F_6 but is *Even*. The first *Odd* step is *trivial* and the second *Even* step could be considered *semi-trivial* since it resulted in the *FIRST* $n_{i_{plus}} \in F_6 \pmod{2} \equiv 0$. Note that the first *Odd* step produces $n_{i_{plus}} = 92$ which is *Even* but it is still *trivial* because because $n_{i_{plus}} = 92 \notin F_6$ ($92 \in F_7$).

$$46 \in F_6 \in \{n \mid 2^{6-1} + 1 \leq n \leq 2^6\}$$

Since $n_{i_{plus}} = 46$ is *Even* it will immediately be divided by 2 to become the $23 = \text{FIRST } n_{i_{plus}} \in F_5$ and is *Odd*. It plots on the Irregular Finite Sub-set Membership Line for Sub-set F_5 in Figure 3. This is a *non-trivial* step.

$$23 \in F_5 \in \{n \mid 2^{5-1} + 1 \leq n \leq 2^5\}$$

Since $n_i = 23$ is *Odd*, the sequence past $n_{i_{plus}} = 23$ will travel below the Irregular Finite Sub-set Membership Line for Sub-set F_4 in Figure 3.

$$f(F_4) = \lceil \log_2(359) + p * (\log_2(3) - 1) \rceil - 4$$

for 3 *Odd* steps and 2 *Even* steps until $n_{i_{plus}} = 20$, which is *still* a member of Sub-set F_5 but is *Even*. The first 4 steps are *trivial*, while the last *Even* step could be considered *semi-trivial* since it resulted in the *FIRST* $n_{i_{plus}} \in F_5 \pmod{2} \equiv 0$. Note again that, in this 5 step sequence, the other *Even* $n_{i_{plus}} \in \{80, 40\} \notin F_5$ and are therefore *trivial*.

$$20 \in F_5 \in \{n \mid 2^{5-1} + 1 \leq n \leq 2^5\}$$

Since $n_{i_{plus}} = 20$ is *Even* it will immediately be divided by 2 to become the $10 = \text{FIRST } n_i \in F_4$ and the *FIRST* $n_{i_{plus}} \in F_4 \pmod{2} \equiv 0$. It plots on the Irregular Finite Sub-set Membership Line for Sub-set F_4 in Figure 3. This is a *non-trivial* step.

$$10 \in F_4 \in \{n \mid 2^{4-1} + 1 \leq n \leq 2^4\}$$

Since $n_{i_{plus}} = 10$ is *Even* it will immediately be divided by 2 to become the $5 = \text{FIRST } n_i \in F_3$ and is *Odd*. It plots on the Irregular Finite Sub-set Membership Line for Sub-set F_3 in Figure 3. This is a *non-trivial* step.

$$5 \in F_3 \in \{n \mid 2^{3-1} + 1 \leq n \leq 2^3\}$$

Since $n_{i_{plus}} = 5$ is *Odd*, the sequence past $n_{i_{plus}} = 5$ will travel below the Irregular Finite Sub-set Membership Line for Sub-set F_2 in Figure 3.

$$f(F_2) = \lceil \log_2(359) + p * (\log_2(3) - 1) \rceil - 2$$

for 1 *Odd* step until $n_i = 8$ which is *also* a member of Sub-set F_3 but is *Even*. This step could be considered *semi-trivial* since it resulted in the *FIRST* $n_{i_{plus}} \in F_3 \pmod{2} \equiv 0$.

$$8 \in F_3 \in \{n \mid 2^{3-1} + 1 \leq n \leq 2^3\}$$

Since $n_{i_{plus}} = 8$ is *Even*, it will immediately be divided by 2 to become $4 = \text{FIRST } n_i \in F_2$ and the *FIRST* $n_{i_{plus}} \in F_2 \pmod{2} \equiv 0$. It plots on the Irregular Finite Sub-set Membership Line for Sub-set F_2 in Figure 3. This is a *non-trivial* step.

$$4 \in F_2 \in \{n \mid 2^{2-1} + 1 \leq n \leq 2^2\}$$

Since $n_{i_{plus}} = 4$ is *Even*, it will immediately be divided by 2 to become $2 = \text{FIRST } n_i \in F_1$ and the *FIRST* $n_{i_{plus}} \in F_1 \pmod{2} \equiv 0$. It plots on the Irregular Finite Sub-set Membership Line for Sub-set F_1 in Figure 3. This is a *non-trivial* step. Note that 2 is the *ONLY* member of Sub-set F_1

$$2 \in F_1 \in \{n \mid 2^{1-1} + 1 \leq n \leq 2^1\}$$

There have been 17 *Even* and 16 *Odd* Steps, so the Energy Level (*EL*) is 17.

$$\log_2(359) + 16 * (\log_2(3) - 1) \approx 17.84724 > EL \Rightarrow \therefore n_i \neq 1$$

Finally, since $n_{i_{plus}} = 2$ is *Even*, it will immediately be divided by 2 to become $1 = \text{FIRST } n_i \in F_0$ and is *Odd*. It plots on the Irregular Finite Sub-set Membership Line for Sub-set F_0 in Figure 3. This is a *non-trivial* step. Note that 1 is the *ONLY* member of Sub-set F_0 and starts the only known terminal loop sequence $\{1, 2, 1, 2, \dots \infty\}$.

$$1 \in F_0 \in \{n \mid n = 1\}$$

There have been 18 *Even* and 16 *Odd* Steps, so the Energy Level (*EL*) is 18.

$$\log_2(359) + 16 * (\log_2(3) - 1) \text{ is still } \approx 17.84724 < EL \Rightarrow \therefore n_i = 1$$

Note that $\lceil \log_2(359) + 16 * (\log_2(3) - 1) \rceil = 18 = \text{OEL}$ (One Energy Level)

$$\text{Note that } \lceil \log_2(359) + 16 * (\log_2(3) - 1) \rceil \neq \lceil \log_2(359) \rceil + 16 * (\log_2(3) - 1)$$

At no Step prior to $n_i = 1$ did the *EL* exceed $\log_2(359) + p * (\log_2(3) - 1)$

8.6. Proof Conclusion. It has been shown that:

- By the recursive application of the Identical and Alternating Equivalence Parity Theorem and Energy Value $> (\log_2(3) - 1)$ Theorem Proofs, that for all $n_i \in F_q$ there must exist a $\text{Step}_{i_{plus}}$ where $n_{i_{plus}} \in F_{q-1}$
- All $n_O \in F_j$ will sequentially pass through intervening Sub-sets $\{F_j, F_{j-1}, F_{j-2}, \dots F_0\}$ eventually reaching Sub-set F_0 , whose only member is 1.

Therefore the Energy Level $\geq \log_2(n_{Original}) + p * (\log_2(3) - 1)$ Theorem is true. \square

9. REDUCTIO AD ABSURDUM COLLATZ CONJECTURE THEOREM

Theorem 9.1. *The Collatz Conjecture is true*

Proof. Proof of Collatz Conjecture is provided by proof of the four theorem:

- (1) Identical and Alternating Equivalence Parity Theorem 5.1
- (2) Energy Value $> (\log_2(3) - 1)$ Theorem 6.1
- (3) No Terminal Loop Sequence other than $\{1, 2, 1, 2, \dots \infty\}$ Theorem 7.1
- (4) Energy Level $\geq \log_2(n_{Original}) + p * (\log_2(3) - 1)$ Theorem 8.1

The sufficiency of the proof is further emphasized by evaluation of:

- (1) Weighted Arithmetic Mean Unsolved Energy Values (\overline{UEV}_{W_i})
 - As Steps approach ∞ , $\overline{UEV}_{W_\infty}$ approaches *EEV*

- (2) Cumulative Probability Distribution Percent Curves versus Proof Lines
 - Always a point of intersection no matter how low a $\% > 0$ is calculated
- (3) Cumulative Exactability Distribution Percent Curves versus Proof Line
 - There is always a point of intersection with the $n_i < n_O$ Proof Line, no matter how low a $\% > 0$ is calculated and this point of intersection is always at an earlier Step_i than for Probability
 - “Exactability” is not another name for Probability without Replacement since the Short-Cut Collatz Function is not truly random function. As was proved by the Identical and Alternating Equivalence Parity Theorem and the Energy Value $> (\log_2(3) - 1)$ Theorem, it is simply an exact and accurate pruning of an infinite non-random pure binomial expansion forest, comprised of infinite non-skewed degenerate trees²⁵, to remove any tree, whose root, when a branch is identical to the root of another tree, is larger than the root of the other tree.

Every doubling of the sample size increases the
 “Exactability” by 1 Step and adds a row
 to the Pascal-like Triangle or Matrix.

- As the Number of Steps at the intersection with the $n_i < n_O$ Proof Line increases toward ∞ , the ratio $\frac{\text{Probability}\%}{\text{Exactability}\%}$ at that intersection continues to increase and therefore, due to the proven Exactable nature of the Short-cut Collatz function, these curves show that:

The Collatz Conjecture is
 “much, much more than Probable” to be true.

Finally by reductio ad absurdum, examining the most extreme possible Equally partitioned INFINITE Sub-sets (I_j) of \mathbb{N}_1 that might possibly never intersect with a proof line, by following a sequence of infinite *Odd* steps and remaining at the Base Energy Level (*BEL*), we find that this Probability or Exactability $\% \approx 0$ which would be a straight line along the x -axis.

As was shown in the proof, the only integers that could *possibly* meet this requirement, will be members of the Sub-set, where $x = \infty$, where $I_{(2^\infty - 1)} = \{n \mid n = 2^\infty - 1 + m * 2^\infty \text{ where } m \in \mathbb{N}_0\}$, with a parity sequence of $2_1 2_2 2_3 \dots 2_\infty$ and $EL = \frac{0}{\infty} = 0 = BEL$ but, as was shown in the proof, 50% of this Sub-set will have the Alternate Parity Sequence at $\text{Step}_{\infty+1}$.

As proved in the Identical and Alternating Equivalence Parity Theorem, at each $\text{Step}_{\infty_{plus}}$ past Step_∞ , the Sub-set $I_{(2^\infty - 1)}$ must be sequentially evenly partitioned, to maintain Identical Parity for that new Sub-set. This again leads to the formation of another Pascal’s Triangle starting at Step_∞ . Pascal’s Triangles, inside of Pascal’s Triangles, inside of Pascal’s Triangles ...²⁶, leading to a logical reductio ad absurdum proof.

Therefore, due to the proven pure binomial expansion of the Short-cut Collatz function and the exactability of the proof that eventually for all n_O there exist a Step_i where $n_i < n_O$ and a $\text{Step}_{i_{plus}}$ where $n_{i_{plus}} = 1$, it is proved logically,

²⁵The roots of all degenerate trees $\in I_1$ of Cardinality \mathbb{N}_0 where $I_1 = \{n \mid 1 + m * 2^0 \text{ and } m \in \{0, 1, 2, \dots, 2^\infty - 1\}\}$. Each degenerate tree would have a unique parity sequence up to Step_∞ .

²⁶Turtles, on top of Turtles, on top of Turtles - Although this saying was originally used as reductio ad absurdum proof of the untruth of a Theorem, in this case it proves the truth.

mathematically and by reductio ad absurdum, that the Collatz Conjecture is true. \square

10. A PARABLE, CONSEQUENCES AND OTHER INTERESTING ITEMS

10.1. A Drunken Sailor always get home (eventually).

A Parable of the Proof

A drunken sailor leaves a pub and heads back to his ship.²⁷ He knows that his ship is somewhere in a North *'ish*-East *'ish* sort of direction. His head is a little fuzzy but he is certain it was more North *'ish* than East *'ish*. He will only go either 1 block North or 1 block East at a time before making his next fuzzy headed choice. He is stubborn, so he will never go backwards. So over all he continues wandering in a more North *'ish* than East *'ish* direction.²⁸

Luckily for the sailor, most of his shipmates are also out and about and like the sailor are drunken. The first time that the sailor goes far enough North so that the number of North blocks travelled divided by the number of East blocks travelled gets more than *.6 'ish* (more exactly $\approx 0.584962500721156$ *'ish*), the sailor sees another pub and realizes he is “thirsty” again. He enters, meets a shipmate and they quickly quench their “thirst” and head out to try to find the ship again.

A while later (how long we never find out), after heading again in a North *'ish*-East *'ish* sort of direction, the two sailors, find *another* pub (also “magically” about *.6 'ish* further North than East from the last pub) and again realizing they were both “thirsty”, they enter and *again* find more shipmates.

This continues, over and over again, until the whole crew of drunken sailors is traveling en masse in a vague North *'ish*-East *'ish* sort of direction with most of them on the same street as the original drunken sailor but with an ever diminishing number of sailors on the side streets.

Eventually the noise of this rowdy bunch draws the attention of the authorities and they call the Ships Captain (#1) and his First Mate (#2), who have been enjoying a fine dinner with the mayor and are quite sober. The Captain and First Mate quickly round up most of the ships company and direct them in a Exactly North-East direction directly to the ship.

The few stragglers that are left will continue to move in a more North *'ish* than East *'ish* direction and, if the Captain waits long enough for the stragglers, eventually, the ship’s company will be at full strength, if a little (or a lot) hung-over.

10.2. **Outliers where $EV > EEV$ but $n_i \not\leq n_{Original}$ beyond the first time.**

It has been proven that, at the first Step_{*i*} where $EV > EEV$, that $n_i < n_{Original}$. Although not needed for this proof, it will also be true for most $n_{Original}$ at all steps from 1 until $n_i = 1$ that, if $EV > EEV$, then $n_i < n_{Original}$.

However, for $n_{Original} \leq 4614, 593$ Outliers (including Even $n_{Original}'s$) were found, that where even though the $n_{Original}$ solved to $n_i < n_{Original}$ at Step_{*i*}, there are instances, in some cases multiple instances, where $n_{i_{plus}} > n_{Original}$ at a later Step_{*i_{plus}*}, even though $EV > EEV$ at Step_{*i_{plus}*}.

The first outlier occurs at $n_{Original} = 7$, which initially solves to $5 < 7$ at Step₇ with an $EV = .75 > EEV$ but solves to $8 > 7$ at Step₈ even though it still has an $EV = .6 > EEV$.

²⁷The author takes a liberty afforded to him by having once been a member of this fine profession and having successfully returned to my ship after liberty calls in many ports.

²⁸Since the sailor *knows* that the ship is in a more North *'ish* than East *'ish* direction he performs a *biased* random walk versus a *pure* random walk.

The last outlier occurs at $n_{Original} = 4614$, which initially solves to $2307 < 4614$ at Step₁ with an $EV = Undefined > EEV$ but solves to $4616 > 4614$ at Step₇₃ even though it still has an $EV \approx 0.58695652173913 > EEV$.

If, at Step _{i} , the value of $|w|$, where w is negative, (w is from Equation 4.41) is close enough to 0 then if the EV_{New} since $n_i < n_{Original}$ is not also $> (\log_2(3) - 1)$ then at a future Step _{i_{plus}} , there is a possibility that $n_{i_{plus}} > n_i$ and therefore a possibility that $n_{i_{plus}} > n_{Original}$ even though the Over-all $EV > EEV$.

Since the lowest possible values of $|w|$ after the first time $EV > EEV$ increase as $n_{Original}$ increases, there is a point at which this possibility should no longer exist. Even if another outlier did exist, it would not invalidate this proof.

10.3. Mirror Parity Sequences. One consequence of the validity of the Collatz Conjecture is that, since at Step _{i} , every possible sequence up to Step _{i} will be followed by ∞ integers, then for every positive integer taken through Step _{i} , there will be:

- ∞ integers that follow **an Identical** parity sequence up to Step _{i}
- ∞ integers that follow **a Mirror** parity sequence up to Step _{i}
 - **Mirror** integers will always have opposite initial parity.

In the example (Figure 13), the sequence for 27 (The Test Integer = TI with 2 digits which solves to 1 in 70 Short-cut Collatz Steps) is plotted along with the sequence for the **first (lowest value)** Mirror Integer (MI with 30 digits which solves to 1 in 598 Short-cut Collatz Steps) that mirrors the TI sequence up to Step₁₀₀. The MI undergoes 2 *Even* Steps before it first becomes *Odd*.

$$MI = 471, 118, 234, 108, 803, 797, 791, 324, 418, 132$$

$$MI_{1^{st} \text{ Odd}} = 117, 779, 558, 527, 200, 949, 447, 831, 104, 533$$

The sequence for an additional Integer designated the Example Break Away Integer (BA with 15 digits which solves to 1 in 111 Short-cut Collatz Steps) that mirrors the TI sequence up to Step₄₉ and is identical to the MI sequence up to Step₄₉ is plotted. The BA also undergoes 2 *Even* Steps before it first becomes *Odd*.

$$BA = 556, 440, 017, 350, 740$$

$$BA_{1^{st} \text{ Odd}} = 139, 110, 004, 337, 685$$

The Example Break Away Integer (BA) is the first (lowest value) Integer that mirrors the TI sequence up to Step₄₉. The Example Break Away Integer (BA) is the first (lowest value) Member of the Sub-set $I_j \in \{j \mid j + m * 2^x \text{ where } m \in \mathbb{N}_0 \text{ and } x = 49 \text{ and } j = BA\}$.²⁹

If the Infinite Sub-set $I_j \in \{n \mid BA + m * 2^{49} \text{ where } m \in \mathbb{N}_0\}$ was limited to a Finite Sub-set $I_j \in \{j \mid BA + m * 2^{49} \text{ where } m \in \{0, 1, 2, \dots, (2^{49} - 1)\}\}$ and all members of the Sub-set were plotted for all Steps up to Step₉₈, they would follow the MI sequence up to Step₄₉ and then split to form a perfect Pascal's Triangle % Distribution shown in the example (Figure 13) up to Step₉₈.³⁰

²⁹ **MI is a member of this Infinite Sub-set.** $MI = BA + 836874097325341 * 2^{49}$

³⁰ There will be **only one member** of this **Finite Sub-set** which, after Step₄₉, will undergo **continuous** Odd Steps until Step₉₈ and **only one member** of this **Finite Sub-set** which, after Step₄₉, will undergo **continuous** Even Steps until Step₉₈

FIGURE 13. Mirror Integer and Break Away Integer of Test Integer 27

10.4. **Slope of Energy Level Curves (ELC) at EEV.** Not necessary for the proof. Utilizing Figure 1:

First Derivative of ELC	$\frac{-L}{(i-L)^2}$
Given:	$ELV_{Step_i} = \frac{(L)}{i-(L)}$
Solve for i , where $ELV = EEV$	$i = \frac{L}{EEV} + L$
Substituting into First Derivative	$\frac{-L}{(\frac{L}{EEV} + L - L)^2}$
\therefore Slope of ELC at EEV	$-\frac{1}{L} * EEV^2$
\therefore Slope Intercept Line Equation	$-\frac{1}{L} * EEV^2 * i + (EEV^2 + 2 * EEV)$
y Intercept	$EEV^2 + 2 * EEV$
	$(\log_2(3))^2 - 1$
$\therefore y$ Intercept	≈ 1.51210612869226

10.5. **Dyck Paths.** Although not critical to this proof of the Collatz Conjecture, two different forms of Non-Standard Dyck Paths were found.

- (1) Using a grid where the x -axis is *Odd Steps* (p) and y -axis is *Even Steps* (q) and a Diagonal with $slope = EEV = \log_2(3) - 1$ versus the Standard Dyck Path Diagonal of $slope = 1$, the Total Unsolved Paths that do not exceed the Diagonal $n_i < n_O$ Proof Limit, where $EEL > p*EEV$, at each *Odd Step* (p), are tabulated at the top of Table 5 and below. The number of these Dyck Paths at each *Odd Step* (p) is also equal to the value of $EL_{(EEL-1)}$ for *Odd Step* ($p + 1$). The sequence of numbers in these Non-Standard Dyck Paths were previously connected to the Collatz Conjecture, again by Dr. Winkler, in [OEIS A100982][13] and associated [OEIS A186008][14].

$$\begin{aligned} & \text{Total Unsolved Paths}_p \text{ Odd Step}_{p_0} \text{ to Odd Step}_{p_{14}...} \\ & \in \{1, 1, 1, 2, 3, 7, 12, 30, 85, 173, 476, 961, 2652, 8045, 17637, \dots\} \end{aligned}$$

- (2) Using the Originally Conceived Plot (Figure 1), presents a unique twist on the Dyck Paths. Instead of *Up* and *Horizontal* Steps, it has *Increasing Diagonal* and *Concave-up Decreasing Curves* Steps. Instead of a limit with $slope = 1$ and a y -intercept = 0, it has a $slope = 0$ and a y -intercept = $\log_2(3) - 1$.

The Total Unsolved Sum for each Step $_i$ in as tabulated in Pascal-like Triangle of UNSOLVED Numerators of Reduced Fractional (UN)% Distribution Results at each Energy Level (Table 3) represent, at each Step $_i$, the Total Unsolved Paths that do not exceed the Straight Line formed by the EEV in Figure 1. Therefore, the numbers, as recorded in [OEIS A076227][8], by definition, represent the Dyke Paths at Step $_i$, although the limit line and step shapes differs structurally from the standard.

$$\begin{aligned} & \text{Total Unsolved Paths}_i \text{ Sequence Step}_{i_0} \text{ to Step}_{i_{24}...} \\ & \in \{1, 1, 1, 2, 3, 4, 8, 13, 19, 38, 64, 128, 226, 367, 734, 1295, 2114, \\ & 4228, 7495, 14990, 27328, 46611, 93222, 168807, 286581, \dots\} \end{aligned}$$

10.5.1. *Another Dyck Path correlation, of interest and possible future research.* If the results as tabulated in the Pascal-like Triangle of UNSOLVED Numerators of Reduced Fractional (UN)% Distribution Results at each Energy Level (Table 3) are added in an *upward left to right diagonal* direction (Similar to Fibonacci Numbers in Pascals Triangle), the new results are identical with the Dyke Path sequence (1, 1, 1, 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 9, 14, 20, 27, 47, 74, 109) found in [OEIS A191321][15] up to entry 15. After entry 15, the results and the entries in A191321 are no longer identical to each other, although there are hints of a relationship (Table 8).

$$\begin{aligned} A191321_{1 \text{ to } 15} &= (1, 1, 1, 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 9, 14, 20, 27, 47, 74, 109,) \\ Results_{1 \text{ to } 15} &= (1, 1, 1, 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 9, 14, 20, 27, 47, 74, 109,) \\ A191321_{16 \text{ to } 26...} &= (153, 262, 415, 622, 894, 1516, 2410, 3653, 5335, 8988, 14323, \dots) \\ Results_{16 \text{ to } 26...} &= (183, 292, 445, 652, 1097, 1749, 2673, 3946, 6619, 10565, 16223, \dots) \end{aligned}$$

Although there appears to be evidence of a relationship between these two sequences, the relationship of these two sequences is not required for the proof of the Collatz Conjecture and, in the interest of the timely publication of this paper, this relationship will not be pursued (further down the rabbit-hole) at this time.

TABLE 8. A191321 DYCK PATH - Equal versus ~~Equal~~

Pascal-like Triangle of UNSOLVED Numerators of Reduced Fractional (UN)% Distribution Results at each Energy Level for Integers $n \in \{1, 2, 3, \dots, 2^x\}$ where $x \geq 13$ from Step 1 to Step 25 where Dyke Numbers (D) Equal or Equal to A191321								
		Equal	Equal	Equal	Equal	Equal	Equal	Equal
STEP _i		D = 1				+30	+30+173	+150+173+961
0	1	D = 1				+30	+60+173	+270+346+961
1	1	D = 1				+30	+90+173	+420+519+961
2	1	D = 1	D = 2			+30	+120+173	
3	1	1	D = 3					
4	1	2	D = 4					
5	1	3	D = 5	D = 9				
6	1	4	3	D = 14				
7	1	5	7	D = 20				
8	1	6	12	D = 27	D = 47			
9	1	7	18	12	D = 74			
10	1	8	25	30	D = 109	D = 183		
11	1	9	33	55	30	D = 292		
12	1	10	42	88	85	D = 445		
13	1	11	52	130	173	D = 652	D = 1097	
14	1	12	63	182	303	173	D = 1749	
15	1	13	75	245	485	476	D = 2673	
16	1	14	88	320	730	961	D = 3946	D = 6619
17	1	15	102	408	1050	1691	961	D = 10565
18	1	16	117	510	1458	2741	2652	D = 16223
19	1	17	133	627	1968	4199	5393	2652
20	1	18	150	760	2595	6167	9592	8045
21	1	19	168	910	3355	8762	15759	17637
22	1	20	187	1078	4265	12117	24521	33396
23	1	21	207	1265	5343	16382	36638	57917
24	1	22	228	1472	6608	21725	53020	94555
25	1	23	250	1700	8080	28333	74745	147575

LIST OF FIGURES

1	Originally Conceived Plot with Starting Integer 359	7
2	Reimagined Plot with Starting Integer 359	8
3	Finite Sub-set Membership Lines with Starting Integer 359	9
4	Reimagined Plot of $n \in \{1, 2, 3, \dots, 16777216(2^{24})\}$	10
5	Plot of $n \in \{16777217(2^{24} + 1), 16777218, 16777219, \dots, 33554432(2^{25})\}$	12
6	Plot of $n \in \{1, 8193, 16385, \dots, 67100673\}$	13
7	ZOOMED Plot of $n \in \{1, 8193, 16385, \dots, 67100673\}$	14
8	Weighted Arithmetic Mean up to Step 456	17
9	Example 3D Views of Folded Cumulative Probability Distribution and Percent Curves	19
10	Folded Cumulative Probability Distribution Percent Curves	21
11	Sample Cumulative Exactability Distribution Percent Curves	22
12	Cumulative Exactability versus Probability Distribution Percent Curves	23
13	Mirror Integer and Break Away Integer of Test Integer 27	60

LIST OF TABLES

1	Pascal's Triangle of Numerators of Reduced Fractional ($N_{L_{Step_i}}$) %	11
2	Alternating Parity at 417 th Step when adding 2^{416} to TI	15
3	Pascal-like Unsolved Numerators of Reduced Fractional ($UN_{L_{Step_i}}$)%	16

4	Pascal Matrix Folded Cumulative Probability and Conservative 10% Points	18
5	Pascal-like Matrix Cumulative Exactability and Conservative 10% Points	20
6	Limited Example of $N_{L_{\text{Step}_i}}$	33
7	Limited Example of $UN_{L_{\text{Step}_i}}$	35
8	A191321 DYCK PATH - Equal versus Equal	62

REFERENCES

(Sorted in order of citation)

- [1] Friedrich Von Schiller, *The Robbers - Translated from German*, Project Gutenberg (1781). <https://www.gutenberg.org/files/6782/6782-h/6782-h.htm>.
- [2] *Collatz conjecture*, Wikipedia (2024). https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Collatz_conjecture.
- [3] Richard Guy, *Unsolved problems in number theory*, Springer Science & Business Media, 2004. <https://books.google.com/books?id=1AP2CEGxTkgC&pg=PA330>.
- [4] Jeffrey C Lagarias, *The Ultimate Challenge: The $3x + 1$ Problem*, American Mathematical Society, 2010.
- [5] Mike Winkler, *On the Structure and the Behavior of Collatz $3n + 1$ Sequences*, arXiv, posted on 2021 (v1 2014), DOI 10.48550/arXiv:1412.0519. <https://arxiv.org/abs/1412.0519v2>.
- [6] ———, *New Results on the Stopping Time Behavior of the Collatz $3x + 1$ Function*, arXiv, posted on 2021 (v1 2015), DOI 10.48550/arXiv:1504.00212. <https://arxiv.org/abs/1504.00212v4>.
- [7] ———, *The Recursive Stopping Time Structure of the $3x+1$ Function*, arXiv, posted on 2024 (v1 2017), DOI 10.48550/arXiv.1709.03385. <https://arxiv.org/abs/1709.03385v4>.
- [8] OEIS Foundation Inc., *Number of surviving Collatz residues mod 2^n .*, Entry A076227 in *The On-Line Encyclopedia of Integer Sequences*, OEIS Foundation Inc. (2024). <https://oeis.org/A076227>.
- [9] Terence Tao, *Almost all orbits of the Collatz map attain almost bounded values*, Forum of Mathematics, Pi **10** (2022), e12, DOI 10.1017/fmp.2022.8. <https://arxiv.org/abs/1909.03562v4>.
- [10] Kevin Hartnett, *Mathematician proves huge result on dangerous problem*, Quanta Magazine (2019). <https://www.quantamagazine.org/mathematician-proves-huge-result-on-dangerous-problem-20191211>.
- [11] David Barina, *Convergence verification of the Collatz problem*, The Journal of Supercomputing **77** (2021), no. 3, 2681–2688.
- [12] OEIS Foundation Inc., *Number of digits in the base-2 representation of 3^n .*, Entry A020914 in *The On-Line Encyclopedia of Integer Sequences*, OEIS Foundation Inc. (2024). <https://oeis.org/A020914>.
- [13] ———, *Number of admissible sequences of order j ; related to $3x+1$ problem and Wagon's constant.*, OEIS Foundation Inc. (2024). <https://oeis.org/A100982>.
- [14] ———, *Length of Collatz dropping time patterns in A186008.*, OEIS Foundation Inc. (2024). <https://oeis.org/A186009>.
- [15] ———, *Number of dispersed Dyck paths of length n (i.e., Motzkin paths of length n with no $(1,0)$ steps at positive heights) having only ascents of even length (an ascent is a maximal sequence of consecutive $(1,1)$ -steps).*, OEIS Foundation Inc. (2024). <https://oeis.org/A191321>.

9734 ALISTER DR., MELBOURNE, FL 32940
 Email address: Kenneth.Hutchings@yahoo.com